

MSc thesis in Geoecology

Eberhard Karls University of Tübingen
Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences
Department of Geoscience

The Mid to Late Miocene Pedogenic Carbonate Derived $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ Signature of Irsee and Hammerschmiede, South Germany

By

Ranasish Roy Chowdhury

Matriculation No. 4136161

Year: 2019

Supervisor(s):

Prof. Dr. Madelaine Böhme

Dr. Heinrich Taubald

Declaration on authorship:

I herewith confirm that to best of my knowledge this thesis has been composed by myself based on my masterwork and matters adopted directly and/or indirectly from other sources are duly cited.

Ranasish Roy Chowdhury

.....
Ranasish Roy Chowdhury

Place: Tübingen
.....

Date: 29.05.2019
.....

Dedicated

To

“Those who give their all to the society but receive nothing”

– Sarat Chandra Chattopadhyay (1876 – 1938)

SUMMARY:

The Miocene Epoch was important because of its several climatic cycles that include extreme warming and cooling. Afterwards of the Mid Miocene Climatic Optimum (MMCO) there was an abrupt cooling and drying. Simultaneous changes in the geosphere had paved the way for Graminoid establishment and subsequent faunal evolution in the Paratethys realm. For a better understanding of the concerned paleocosystem this study takes an effort to reconstruct the vegetation and climate pattern of the transition phase between the Middle Miocene to the Late Miocene (12.207 – 11.154 Ma) from the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values of the pedogenic carbonates from Hammerschmiede outcrop and Irsee drill-core of the North Alpine Foreland Basin (NAFB).

The carbon isotopic range from -10.90‰ to -4.01‰ is denoting that the carbonate crystallisation took place in a C3 dominant paleoecosystem however with declining of the timescale, presence of C4 plant taxa is obvious. The oxygen isotope with a range from -7.21‰ to -4.74‰ bears the marks of global cooling events (Mi) however the evaporative Paratethys Sea and the warm Atlantic Ocean inflow which resulted in *amount effect* were supposed to have overwhelmed the Mi effects. This geochemical study which is first of its kind in this section of the NAFB plateau proposes a C4 vegetation development at here under a relatively dry and possibly warm climate from the verge of the Early Late Miocene.

Key word: Miocene, transition, NAFB, pedogenic carbonate, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, Paratethys, *amount effect*, C3, C4

Zusammenfassung:

Das Miozän war wichtig wegen seiner mehreren Klimazyklen, zu denen auch extreme Erwärmung und Kühlung gehören. Nach dem mittleren miozänen Klimaoptimum (MMCO) kam es zu einer abrupten Abkühlung und Trocknung. Gleichzeitige Veränderungen in der Geosphäre hatten den Weg für die graminoiden Etablierung und die anschließende faunale Evolution im Bereich der Paratethys geebnet. Zum besseren Verständnis des betroffenen Paläokosystems wird in dieser Studie versucht, die Vegetations- und Klimamuster der Übergangsphase zwischen dem Mittelmiozän und dem Spätmiozän (12.207 - 11.154 Ma) aus

den $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ und $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ Werten der pedogenen Karbonate aus dem Aufschluss Hammerschmiede und dem Irsee-Bohrkern des Nordalpenvorlandes (NAFB) zu rekonstruieren.

Der Kohlenstoffisotopenbereich von -10.90‰ bis -4.01‰ deutet darauf hin, dass die Karbonatkristallisation in einem C3-dominanten Paläoökosystem stattgefunden hat, jedoch ist mit dem Rückgang der zeitlichen, Präsenz von C4-Pflanzentaxa offensichtlich. Das Sauerstoffisotop mit einem Bereich von -7.21‰ bis -4.74‰ trägt die Spuren globaler Kühlereignisse (Mi), aber die verdunstende Paratethyssee und der warme Atlantikzufluss, der zu Mengeneffekten führte, sollten die Mi-Effekte überwältigt haben. Diese geochemische Studie, die in diesem Abschnitt des NAFB-Plateaus zum ersten Mal durchgeführt wird, schlägt eine C4-Vegetationsentwicklung hier unter einem relativ trockenen und möglicherweise warmen Klima am Rande des frühen späten Miozäns vor.

Stichwort: Miozän, Übergangsphase, NAFB, $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, pedogenen Karbonate, Paratethys, Mengeneffekten, C3, C4.

Translation Courtesy: Übersetzt mit www.DeepL.com/Translator

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I am obliged to my primary supervisor Prof. Dr. Madelaine Böhme who offered me to pursue this Master thesis and patiently guided me in various phases of the work.

I am grateful to my secondary supervisor Dr. Heinrich Taubald who kindly arranged the isotope analysis from the Erlangen-Nuremberg University and gave valuable suggestions from his busy schedules on the paleotemperature reconstruction from oxygen isotope.

I am thankful to Ms. Agnes Fatz of her nice arrangements for the sample storage and preparations. I wish to thank Mr. Bernd Steinhilber and Mr. Henrik Stöhr for lending their tools for sample preparations. I also thank Mr. Jochen Fuß and Mr. Thomas Lechner for their kind logistics arrangement during the sample collections from Hammerschmiede outcrop. Many thanks to Dr. Hartmut Schluz and Dr. Philipp Munz for their permission to get access to the Irsee drill-core at the sediment core repository of the Tübingen University at Sand Drosselweg.

I would like to thank Dr. Kevin T. Uno, Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory of Columbia University, New York for his personal communication on carbon isotope interpretation. I would also like to extend my thankfulness to Dr. Prosenjit Ghosh, CEaS, IISC Bangalore for imparting practical skills on isotope chemistry in 2014 otherwise it would be difficult for me to pursue this theoretical task. I specially want to say thank you to my best friend in Tübingen, Heiko Hinnerberg who encouraged me to learn the R software and happily answered to my statistical queries.

And finally I have no words to express my love and gratitude to my Parents and Sister — without their financial supports and endless cheer ups I cannot accomplish this course.

CONTENTS

SUMMARY:	i
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	iii
CONTENTS	iv
LIST OF FIGURES:	vi
LIST OF TABLES:	vii
I. INTRODUCTION	1
I.A. Aim of study:.....	1
I.B. Isotope system:.....	2
I.C. $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ link with C3 & C4 photosynthesis:.....	3
I.D. $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and climatic signature:	5
I.E. Pedogenic carbonate:	6
I.F. Pedogenic carbonate & stable isotope relationship:.....	7
I.F.1. PC- $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ significance:.....	8
I.F.2. PC- $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ significance:	9
I.G. Global and regional paleoenvironment during the Mid to Late Miocene transformation:	9
II. GEOGRAPHICAL AND GEOLOGICAL INFORMATION	14
II.A. Geographical information of sampling sites:.....	14
II.B. Geological setting of the sampling sites:	15
II.C. Lithological description of Hammerschmiede (HAM):.....	19
II.D. Lithological description of Irsee drill-core:	20
III. METHODOLOGY	22
III.A. Sample Collection:	22
III.B. Sample preparation:	23
III.B.1. Water screening:.....	23
III.B.2. Oven drying:.....	25
III.B.3. Grinding:	26
III.C. Isotope Analysis:	26
IV. RESULT	27
IV.A. Stratigraphic unit nomenclature:	27
IV.B. Isotope data:.....	28
IV.C. Statistical relationship of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (R^2 and R):	30
IV.C.1. ANOVA Output:.....	31

IV.C.2. Outlier assumption:	31
IV.D. Interpretation of C3 and C4 components (%):	33
IV.E. Disparity of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ profile:	34
V. DISCUSSION	36
V.A. Paleoenvironmental signature of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ cross-plot:	36
V.B. Understanding the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{PC}}$ based paleoecosystem:	37
V.B.1. Paleobiomass percentage:.....	39
V.B.2. Spatiotemporal comparison of $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{PC}}$ in regional scale:.....	40
V.C. Account on the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PC}}$ based paleoclimate:.....	41
V.C.1. Paleoaltitude reconstruction from $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PC}}$:	43
V.C.2. Paleotemperature reconstruction from $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PC}}$:	44
V.C.3. Spatiotemporal comparison of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PC}}$ in regional scale:	44
V.D. Relevance of the Irsee and HAM isotopic signature in light of the Mid to Late Miocene paleoenvironment:	45
VI. CONCLUSION.....	54
REFERENCES	56
LIST OF WEBSITES:	70
LIST OF SOFTWARE:	70
Appendix-1.....	viii
Appendix-2.....	ix
Appendix-3.....	xi
Appendix-4.....	xii

LIST OF FIGURES:

FIGURE 1: CARBON FIXATION PATHWAY OF THE C3, C4 AND CAM PHOTOSYNTHESIS (W. YAMORI ET AL, 2014)..... 4

FIGURE 2: ISOSCAPE OF THE SPATIAL VARIATION OF MEAN ANNUAL D18O IN PRECIPITATION COMPILED FROM THE GNIP STATIONS (BOWEN & WILKINSON, 2002). 6

FIGURE 3: GRAPHICAL RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN PEDOGENIC CARBONATE WITH D¹⁸O & D¹³C. [COURTESY: CLIPART LIBRARY] 8

FIGURE 4: CENOZOIC TIME SCALE WHERE LIGHT GREEN AREA INDICATES THE TIMEFRAME OF THE PRESENT STUDY. (ADAPTED FROM [HTTPS://SKEPTICALSCIENCE.COM/PRINT.PHP?N=2845](https://skepticalscience.com/print.php?n=2845))..... 13

FIGURE 5: TOPOGRAPHICAL AND GEOGRAPHICAL AND MAP OF THE STUDY AREA. (KIRSCHER ET AL., 2016)..... 14

FIGURE 6: SCHEMATIC PALEO GEOGRAPHIC MAP OF THE NORTH ALPINE FORELAND BASIN (NAFB) WITH DIRECTION OF MIDDLE MIOCENE SEDIMENT TRANSPORT [BLACK ARROWS] AND AREAS WITH PREVAILING EROSION [WHITE] AND SEDIMENTATION [YELLOW]. (ROCHOLL ET AL., 2018) 15

FIGURE 7: PALEO GEOGRAPHIC MAP OF THE PARATETHYS REGION DURING THE LATE EARLY BADENIAN [CA. 15–14 MA]) WITH THE LOCATION OF SAMPLED SITES [BLACK TRIANGLES], REFERENCE SITES [RED SQUARES] AND LARGE CALKALINE SILICIC VOLCANIC CENTERS [ORANGE STARS: BVF BÜKKALJA VOLCANIC FIELD, HUNGARY, GM GUTÂI MOUNTAINS, ROMANIA. 1 BISCHOFZELL, 2 HEILSBURG, 3 KRUMBAD, 4 LAIMERING, 5 UNTERNEUL, 6 ZAHLING, 7 HACHELSTUHL, 8 PONHOLZ]. (ROCHOLL ET AL., 2018) 16

FIGURE 8: LOCATION OF MOLASSE BASIN AND TERRESTRIAL DEPOSITS OF THE UPPER FRESHWATER MOLASSE (UFM) IN GERMANY. UFM WITHOUT PEBBLES (LIGHT GREY), UFM WITH PEBBLES (MEDIUM GREY), UFM WITHOUT PEBBLES BUT WITH COAL AND HUMUS (DARK GREY), MAIN DRAINAGE AND SIDE TRIBUTARIES (BLACK ARROWS). (ERONEN AND RÖSSNER, 2007) 17

FIGURE 9: IRSEE DRILL-CORE LITHOLOGY WITH TOPOGRAPHIC LABEL (LEFT) AND HEIGHT LABEL BELOW THE SURFACE (RIGHT). HAMMERSCHMIEDE LITHOLOGY WITH HEIGHT LABEL BELOW THE SURFACE (RIGHT) AND SAMPLING POINTS (LEFT). THE CORRELATION OF IRSEE & HAM IS SHOWN WITH DOTTED LINES. ON TOP WITH TOPOGRAPHIC MAP OF THE LOCATIONS AND CROSS SECTION RANGING FROM THE IRSEE DRILL-CORE TO THE HAM CLAY PIT ARE SHOWN. [AFTER(KIRSCHER ET AL., 2016)] 18

FIGURE 10: A) OUTCROP OF THE HAM CLAYPIT. B) PROMINENT COAL LAYER OF HAM OUTCROP. C) UFM SEDIMENT CLUSTERS AROUND CARBONATE CONCRETES IN HAM. D) PEDOGENIC CARBONATES IN A HAM SAMPLING POINT. 19

FIGURE 11: HAM5 PALEOCHANNEL AND FOSSIL EXCAVATION SITE. 20

FIGURE 12: A) DEEPER SECTIONS OF IRSEE DRILL-CORE WITH MORE CARBONATE CONCRETIONS (BLUE ARROW). B) UPPER SECTIONS OF IRSEE DRILL-CORE SECTION WITH LESSER CARBONATE CONCRETIONS (BLUE ARROW) & SOFT SANDSTONES (YELLOW ARROW). 21

FIGURE 13: A) PEDOGENIC CARBONATE NODULES FROM THE HAMMERSCHMIEDE CLAY PIT. B) PEDOGENIC CARBONATE NODULE BEARING IRSEE DRILL-CORE..... 22

FIGURE 14: WATER SCREENING OF THE SAMPLE. 23

FIGURE 15: A) PEDOGENIC CARBONATE NODULES. B) HANDPICKED WATERSCREENED PEDOGENIC CARBONATES. C) TRANSFERRING OF HANDPICKED PEDOGENIC CARBONATES TO THE FALCON TUBE. 23

FIGURE 16: A) DISSOLVED SEDIMENT IN WARM WATER. B) WATER SCREENING OF THE SAMPLE WITH FINER MESH. C) WASHED CARBONATE NODULES. D) PEDOGENIC CARBONATES AFTER FINAL WATER SCREENING. 24

FIGURE 17: CARBONATE NODULES AFTER FINAL WASH. 24

FIGURE 18: MEMMERT OVEN..... 25

FIGURE 19: A) OVEN DRYING OF SAMPLES WITH PAPER PLUG (YELLOW ARROW). B) OVEN DRIED CARBONATE NODULES. 25

FIGURE 20: A) GRINDING OF CARBONATE NODULES. B) SCRAPPING OF CARBONATE POWDERS WITH CLEAN INCISORS. C) CARBONATE POWDER IN PAPER BOAT FOR TRANSFERRING TO EPPENDROF TUBE. D) EPPENDROF TUBES WITH CARBONATE POWDER.	26
FIGURE 21: AGE CLUSTERING OF THE SAMPLING SITE. ELM- EARLY LATE MIOCENE; LLM-LATE MIDDLE MIOCENE; MMM- MID MIDDLE MIOCENE; EH1- YOUNGER EROSION HIATUS; EH2- OLDER EROSION HIATUS.	27
FIGURE 22: TEMPORAL $D^{13}C$ VARIATION IN IRSEE AND HAM.	28
FIGURE 23: TEMPORAL $D^{18}O$ VARIATION IN IRSEE AND HAM.	29
FIGURE 24: CORRELATION PLOTS BETWEEN THE $D^{13}C$ AND $D^{18}O$	30
FIGURE 25: ANOVA OUTPUT OF THE ENTIRE PROFILE; A) CARBON ISOTOPE. B) OXYGEN ISOTOPE.	31
FIGURE 26: ANOVA OUTPUT OF THE ENTIRE PROFILE WITHOUT 11.222 MA DATA; A) CARBON ISOTOPE. B) OXYGEN ISOTOPE.	32
FIGURE 27: ANOVA OUTPUT OF THE ENTIRE PROFILE WITHOUT 11.222 MA & 11.661 MA DATA;	32
FIGURE 28: C4% IN THE PALEOVEGETATION OF THE ENTIRE PROFILE.	34
FIGURE 29: INCONGRUITY ZONES BETWEEN THE $D^{13}C$ AND $D^{18}O$ VALUES.	34
FIGURE 30: CORRELATION PLOTS BETWEEN THE $D^{13}C$ AND $D^{18}O$	36
FIGURE 31: A) NORMAL Q-Q PLOT FOR $D^{13}C$ DATA. B) NORMAL Q-Q PLOT FOR $D^{18}O$	37
FIGURE 32: THE $D^{13}C$ PROFILE OF THE STUDY SITE FROM THE MID TO LATE MIOCENE TRANSITION. THE C3 UPPER LIMIT OF THE RESPECTIVE TEMPORAL SCALE IS CONSIDERED AFTER B. J. TIPPLE ET AL., 2010 AND I. COJAN ET AL., 2013. THE PINK AREA REPRESENTS BENTHIC $D^{13}C$ BASED AVERAGE $D^{13}C[CO_2]_{ATM}$ 12.9 – 7.9 MA AFTER B.J. TIPPLE ET AL, 2010.	38
FIGURE 33: THE $D^{13}C$ DISTRIBUTION DURING THE LATE MIDDLE MIOCENE IN IRSEE AND HAM.	39
FIGURE 34: C4 CONTRIBUTION (%) IN THE PALEOVEGETATION OF IRSEE AND HAMMERSCHMIEDE AFTER THREE DIFFERENT NEOGENE $\delta^{13}C$ TIME SERIES MODELS. RED DASHED LINE REPRESENTS THE SIGNIFICANT LEVEL OF THE C4 CONTRIBUTION.	40
FIGURE 35: REGIONAL SPATIOTEMPORAL $D^{13}C$ STATUS IN COMPARISON WITH THIS STUDY.	41
FIGURE 36: THE $D^{18}O$ PROFILE OF THE STUDY SITE FROM THE MID TO LATE MIOCENE TRANSITION (LEFT). THE SYNCHRONOUS $D^{18}O$ VALUE OF GLOBAL OCEAN (RIGHT) WHERE THE BLUE PEAKS ARE REPRESENTING COOLING PHASE AND THE RED PEAKS ARE REPRESENTING WARMING PHASE.	42
FIGURE 37: THE $D^{18}O$ DISTRIBUTION DURING THE LATE MIDDLE MIOCENE IN IRSEE AND HAM.	43
FIGURE 38: REGIONAL SPATIOTEMPORAL $D^{18}O$ STATUS IN COMPARISON WITH THIS STUDY.	45
FIGURE 39: THE $D^{13}C$ AND $D^{18}O$ PROFILES FROM THE MID TO LATE MIOCENE TRANSITION IN THE IRSEE AND HAM. .	46
FIGURE 40: COMPARISON OF $D^{13}C$ VALUES OF THIS STUDY WITH CONCOMITANT GLOBAL CLIMATIC CONDITIONS.	48
FIGURE 41: COMPARISON OF $D^{18}O$ VALUES OF THIS STUDY WITH CONCOMITANT GLOBAL CLIMATIC CONDITIONS.	51
FIGURE 42: GLOBAL AND REGIONAL GEOCLIMATIC EVENTS CONCOMITANT WITH THIS STUDY AND THE CHANGING PALEOENVIRONMENT MODEL OF THE IRSEE AND HAM. THE BLACK ARROWS INDICATE THE DIRECTION OF INCREASING MAGNITUDE OF THE RESPECTIVE EVENT. [COURTESY: CLIPART LIBRARY]	53

LIST OF TABLES:

TABLE 1: SUMMARIZED DATA OF THE $\delta^{13}C$ & $\delta^{18}O$ VALUES FROM THE ENTIRE PROFILE	29
TABLE 2: SUMMARISATION OF THE C3 AND C4 VEGETATION IN PERCENTAGE FROM THE $\delta^{13}C_{PC}$ VALUES.	33

I. INTRODUCTION

I.A. Aim of study: In paleontological studies one of the biggest challenges is to find appropriate and reliable proxies for deciphering the past environment. After discovery of the stable isotopes, around a century ago, the challenge was met to many extents. The next issue that comes thereafter is finding suitable subjects for isotope analysis. Often the classical paleontologists are reluctant to share their prized findings for cracking the concerned paleoenvironmental information with the 'isotopeers' ([Fry, 2008](#)). Hence the isotopeers are largely looking for samples which are abundant in nature so that irreversible isotope analyses do not make loopholes in the fossil records. Microfossils such as foraminifera, coccolithophore, diatom, radiolaria meet the criterion well in the marine ecosystem. But in the terrestrial ecosystems getting access to such microfossils is limited. Hence the inorganic carbonate forms like the stalactites, stalagmites, soil carbonates are widely used in this field. Among them the paleosol carbonate *alias* caliche or calcrete are important continental paleoenvironmental indicators ([Catoni et al., 2012](#); [Ghosh et al., 1995](#); [Lee and Hisada, 1999](#)) as they are profuse and widely distributed in the geological records ([Quade et al., 2013](#)) and their stable isotopes signify the environmental influence on the soil forming process unless there is any alteration by diagenesis ([Cerling, 1984](#)).

Stable isotope ratio of carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) from the pedogenic carbonate estimates the local vegetation type (eg. C3, C4) during the carbonate formation time and thus is considered as paleoecological indicator ([Cerling et al., 1989](#)). Whereas stable isotope ratio of oxygen ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$) from the pedogenic carbonate implies the ambient temperature and moisture status during the carbonate formation time ([Leone et al., 2000](#)) and hence is considered as paleoclimatic proxy. In this way the paleosol carbonates are valuable natural archives of the past landscape chronology and biological evolution ([Leone et al., 2000](#)). Their isotope geochemistry study gets momentum from the 1970's ([Cerling, 1984](#); [Cerling et al., 1989](#); [Quade et al., 1989](#)) which has further intensified after the clumped-isotope (Δ_{47}) invention ([Quade et al., 2007](#)). In compliance with such engagements here an effort has been taken to reconstruct the paleoenvironment of Hammerschmiede during the Middle to the Late

Miocene transition phase using the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of the pedogenic carbonate in my Master thesis.

I.B. Isotope system: Isotopes can be simply defined as atoms of same elements having same no. of protons but different no. of neutrons ([Criss, 1999](#); [Fry, 2008](#); [Hoefs, 2004](#); [Sharp, 2007](#)). Stable traditional and light isotopes are used mostly to explore the paleoenvironmental information as they are mostly available in organic materials and their relative mass differences between isotopes of the same element are large ([Newton, 2010](#)). Mass spectrometer instrument separates and thereafter measures the number of heavy and light isotopes of an element e.g. $^2\text{H}/^1\text{H}$, $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$, $^{15}\text{N}/^{14}\text{N}$, $^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O}$, $^{34}\text{S}/^{32}\text{S}$ of the given sample and a known standard ([Bocherens and Drucker, 2013](#)). The result of the isotopic ratio is expressed as relative abundances and termed as 'delta' (δ or d) values with the unit per mill (‰); this expression can be defined as follow:

$$\delta^{\text{E}X} = \frac{R_X - R_{\text{std}}}{R_{\text{std}}} \times 1000 \text{ ‰} \dots\dots\dots\text{Eq.1}$$

Here $^{\text{E}X}$ represents ^2H , ^{13}C , ^{15}N , ^{18}O , ^{34}S and so on; R_X is the heavy to light isotope ratio of sample X and R_{std} is the heavy to light isotope ratio of the standard. Among the stable isotopes carbon and oxygen have wide range of application in paleoecology and paleoclimatology.

Carbon has many isotopes in nature however only two of them ^{12}C (98.99%) and ^{13}C (1.11%) are stable ([Hoefs, 2004](#)). The international reference standard for $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values is PeeDee Belemnite (PDB) ([Hoefs, 2004](#); [Sharp, 2007](#)). By definition $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value of PDB is '0' ([Sharp, 2007](#)). The carbon isotope fractionation in carbonate, CO_2 , CH_4 under equilibrium is important both for low and high temperature ([Hoefs, 2004](#)).

Oxygen has three stable isotopes: ^{16}O (99.76%), ^{17}O (0.04%) and ^{18}O (0.20%) but due to higher mass difference, the $^{18}\text{O} / ^{16}\text{O}$ is usually informed ([Hoefs, 2004](#)). $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ is either reported in Standard Mean Ocean Water (SMOW) reference scale or in PDB reference scale ([Hoefs, 2004](#); [Sharp, 2007](#)); the latter is applicable for the carbonates from low temperature

([Hoefs, 2004](#); [Sharp, 2007](#)). The conversion of the two standards ([Hoefs, 2004](#)) can be expressed as follow:

$$^{18}\text{O}_{(\text{SMOW})} = 1.03091 \ ^{18}\text{O}_{(\text{PDB})} + 30.91 \dots\dots\dots\text{Eq.2}$$

$$^{18}\text{O}_{(\text{PDB})} = 0.97002 \ ^{18}\text{O}_{(\text{SMOW})} - 29.98 \dots\dots\dots\text{Eq.3}$$

I.C. $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ link with C3 & C4 photosynthesis: Usually plants belonged to cool and wet climate use the C3 photosynthesis whereas that from warm and arid environment ([Fox et al., 2012](#); [Hattersley, 1983](#); [Salisbury and Ross, 1992](#)) and / or low atmospheric $p\text{CO}_2$ ([Cerling et al., 1997](#); [Ehleringer et al., 1997](#); [1991](#); [Fox et al., 2012](#)) follows the C4 photosynthesis. On the other hand the CAM (Crassulacean acid metabolism) plants eg. succulents, cacti have a combination of the C3 and C4 characteristics ([Salisbury and Ross, 1992](#)). In the C3 plants CO_2 is fixed by the enzyme RuBisCo in the bundle sheath cells which yields first a 3-carbon product – phospho glyceric acid (PGA) ([Salisbury and Ross, 1992](#)). The C4 plants, for reducing the internal desiccation and CO_2 loss through photorespiration have evolved Kranz anatomy ([Fox et al., 2012](#); [Sage, 2004](#); [Salisbury and Ross, 1992](#)). As a consequence within their mesophyll cells the atmospheric CO_2 is converted into HCO_3^- by the enzyme carbonic anhydrase (CA) and thereafter bound by the enzyme phospho enol pyruvate carboxylase (PEPcase) as a 4 carbon molecule - oxalo acetic acid (OAA); the OAA then moves into the bundle sheath cells where the nicotinamide di nucleotide phosphate (NADP) frees one mole CO_2 from the OAA which in turn takes part in the Calvin cycle for glucose production ([Salisbury and Ross, 1992](#)).

Due to its importance in evolutionary and ecological contexts, origin of the grassland ecosystem that consists of the different clades of the Poaceae is a topic of much scientific interest for several decades. Poaceae family was appeared during the late Cretaceous and by the mid Paleogene it became dominant in some quarters of the world ([Fox et al., 2012](#); [Quade and Cerling, 1995](#)). Although timing of the C4 origin varied from region to region, but in general it is assumed that from the Oligocene onwards (35-24 Ma) the C4 photosynthesis evolved in the Poaceae family ([Christin et al., 2008](#); [Fox et al., 2012](#); [Sage, 2004](#); [Tippie and Pagani, 2007](#)) and later the C4 dicots like Chenopodiaceae originated (21-15 Ma) ([Sage,](#)

2004). The C4 grasslands during the arid season in presence of low CO₂ globally spread during 8 - 6 Ma ([Behrensmeier et al., 2007](#); [Cerling et al., 1997](#); [Cerling and Quade, 1993](#); [Fox et al., 2012](#); [Tzanova et al., 2015](#)) whereas cacti and succulent plants of the arid climate became diverse from 10.5 Ma onwards ([Arakaki et al., 2011](#); [Tzanova et al., 2015](#)).

Figure 1: Carbon fixation pathway of the C₃, C₄ and CAM photosynthesis (W. Yamori et al, 2014).

The carbon isotope fractionation during carboxylation of ribulose biphosphate by RuBisCo discriminates intensely against ¹³CO₂ in favour of ¹²CO₂ in the C₃ plants where 1 chambered (bundle sheath) photosynthesis rate is slower while the opposite is happened in the C₄ plants where with involvement of 2 chambers (mesophyll & bundle sheath) photosynthesis rate is faster ([Farquhar et al., 1989](#); [Fox et al., 2012](#); [O'Leary, 1981, 1988](#)). Overall apparent

carbon isotope enrichment during CO₂ fixation by C₃ photosynthesis is approximately -19.6‰ ([Passey et al., 2002](#)) and modern C₃ plants have a mean δ¹³C value of about -27‰ (Vienna Peedee belemnite [VPDB]) ([Fox et al., 2012](#)). Whereas apparent isotope enrichment during C₄ photosynthesis is about -4.7‰ ([Passey et al., 2002](#)) and modern C₄ plants have a mean δ¹³C value of about -13‰ (VPDB) ([Fox et al., 2012](#)). Various environmental factors influence net δ¹³C fractionation during photosynthesis, so that both C₃ and C₄ plants exhibit considerable variability about their mean values.

I.D. δ¹⁸O and climatic signature: Multifaceted interactions between the atmosphere, hydrosphere, and lithosphere control the δ¹⁸O variation in the environment. Oceanic δ¹⁸O value primarily controls the δ¹⁸O value of the hydrological cycle through its various physical phases eg. ocean water → water vapour → cloud → precipitation ([Lachniet, 2009](#)). Furthermore several factors control the isotopic composition of the precipitation which includes temperature distance from the moisture source, altitude, seasonality, amount effect etc. ([Sharp, 2007](#)). After the classical paleotemperature equation by Epstein in 1953, the global correlation between the δ¹⁸O of precipitation and the mean annual surface temperature is expressed ([Dansgaard, 1964](#); [Sharp, 2007](#)) as:

$$\delta^{18}\text{O} = 0.69T_{\text{average}} - 13.6 \dots \dots \dots \text{Eq.3}$$

The δ¹⁸O from the terrestrial carbonates are used often to estimate the δ¹⁸O of meteoric water however the interpretation is different from marine setups because of glacial inputs into the latter ([Sharp, 2007](#)). Oxygen isotope ratios of different sources such as speleothems, pedogenic minerals, biogenic minerals, tree cellulose etc. are in use for paleotemperature reconstruction however the quantification success is limited because of lack of comprehension on the δ¹⁸O value of meteoric water ([Dworkin et al., 2005](#)).

Figure 2: Isoscape of the spatial variation of mean annual $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in precipitation compiled from the GNIP stations (Bowen & Wilkinson, 2002).

The development of clumped isotope (Δ_{47}) in the last decade which is measuring of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ coupled in one molecule simultaneously, for instance as $^{13}\text{C}^{18}\text{O}^{16}\text{O}$ ([Zamanian et al., 2016](#)) is a giant leap in isotope geochemistry. In this method the Δ_{47} value in a crystal lattice depends only on the environmental temperature and not on the ambient aqueous matrix ([Ghosh et al., 2006a](#)). Moreover the Δ_{47} derived relationship between environmental temperature and elevation enable to predict upliftment range and relief histories of geological surfaces ([Campani et al., 2012](#); [Ghosh et al., 2006b](#); [Quade et al., 2013](#)). Thus the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and Δ_{47} combination holds the promise for the orogenesis reconstruction in the finest scale ([Quade et al., 2007](#)).

I.E. Pedogenic carbonate: Pedogenic carbonate (PC) is part of the largest terrestrial C pool and the third largest C reservoir of our world ([Catoni et al., 2012](#); [Eswaran et al., 2000](#); [Lal, 2008](#); [Zamanian et al., 2016](#)). Precipitation and temperature primarily control the PC distribution in the nature ([Zamanian et al., 2016](#)). The soil inorganic carbonates (SIC) from which the PC mainly forms, prefer soils where mean annual precipitation (MAP) is less than

about 750 mm - 1000 mm ([Cerling, 1984](#); [Lee and Hisada, 1999](#); [Zamanian et al., 2016](#)) and rarely available in the regions with MAP higher than 1000 mm ([Cerling, 1984](#)). In general PC forms under arid, semi-arid ([Achyuthan, 2003](#); [Achyuthan et al., 2007](#); [Cerling, 1984](#)) to sub-humid climatic conditions with a soil pH 7 or above ([Cerling, 1984](#)). The PC depth profile in the soil horizon is thus allied with mean annual precipitation ([Retallack, 2000, 2005](#)). A greater mean residence time of SIC (~78,000 yrs) than the SOC (upto few centuries) enables the PC isotopes to hold the environmental signature of longer geological time scale ([Schlesinger, 1985](#); [Zamanian et al., 2016](#)). During the soil development, recrystallization and redistribution of the geogenic carbonate (GC), biogenic carbonate (BC) or previously formed PC lead to the new PC formation ([Zamanian et al., 2016](#)). The PC formation has three general phases viz., dissolution of existing SIC pools, movement of dissolved ions in various directions and re-precipitation of the supersaturated of soil solution in respect to CaCO₃ under influence of decreasing soil water content (when evapotranspiration rate is higher) and decreasing pCO₂ ([Robbins, 1985](#); [Salomons and Mook, 1976](#); [Zamanian et al., 2016](#)). The following equation ([Quade et al., 1989](#)) can best describe this complex process simply:

Based on the contribution ratio of the biotic and abiotic processes during PC formation there are around 10 PC-morphotypes ([Zamanian et al., 2016](#)). However in broader sense they can be categorized as stable calcite and vaterite or unstable aragonite. With the increasing temperature, the [CO₃²⁻]/[Ca₂⁺] decreases which prefers aragonite formation over calcite and vaterite ([Zamanian et al., 2016](#)).

I.F. Pedogenic carbonate & stable isotope relationship: Soil water (H₂O) and the soil carbon di oxide (CO₂) from which the PCs develop ([Quade et al., 1989](#)) have their primary source from the infiltrated meteoric water and plant respiration through root hair respectively ([Cerling, 1984](#); [Ghosh et al., 1995](#); [Latorre et al., 1997](#)). Oxygen isotopes of the soil H₂O reflects a number meteoric and orogenic features like amount and seasonality of precipitation, latitude and elevation information of the sampling stations besides ambient

temperature ([Ghosh et al., 1995](#); [Rozanski et al., 1992](#)). The carbon isotope of the soil CO₂ appraises the photosynthetic patterns of local vegetation ([Cerling, 1984](#); [Cerling et al., 1989](#)), aridity ([Garziona et al., 2008](#)) and pCO₂ ([Cerling et al., 1991](#); [Ghosh et al., 1995](#); [Retallack, 2009](#)). Henceforth the authigenic PC-δ¹⁸O and PC-δ¹³C bear the surrounding environmental and ecological signature ([Cerling et al., 1989](#); [Zamanian et al., 2016](#)) which the following graphic is showing [Fig.3].

Figure 3: Graphical relationship between pedogenic carbonate with δ¹⁸O & δ¹³C.
[Courtesy: Clipart Library]

I.F.1. PC-δ¹³C significance: Since the uptake of the heavier carbon isotope (¹³C) in the C₃ plants is lesser than the C₄ plants ([Fox et al., 2012](#)) hence the δ¹³C of CO₂ from C₃ plant respiration (-27‰ on average) differs from that of the C₄ species (-13‰ on average) ([Cerling et al., 1997](#); [Zamanian et al., 2016](#)). Isotopic difference by ¹²CO₂ and ¹³CO₂ diffusion in soil is *ca.* +4.4‰ ([Cerling et al., 1991](#)) and carbonate precipitation *ca.* +11‰ ([Zamanian et](#)

[al., 2016](#)). As a consequence, PC- $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ is enriched by *ca.* 15‰ in comparison to plant respired CO_2 ([Latorre et al., 1997](#); [Zamanian et al., 2016](#)). The resultant values of the PC- $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ are *ca.* -12‰ under pure C3 vegetation and *ca.* +2‰ under pure C4 vegetation ([Zamanian et al., 2016](#)). In reality PC- $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value under the presence of C3 plants has wider average range (-14‰ to -8‰) whereas the PC- $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value higher than the threshold value of -8‰ indicate significant moisture stress and presence of the C4 vegetation ([Latorre et al., 1997](#)).

I.F.2. PC- $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ significance: Rising temperature and subsequent evaporation increment trigger higher $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ enrichment in the PC and henceforth the PC- $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ corresponds with mean annual temperature (MAT) well ([Cerling, 1984](#); [Hsieh et al., 1998a](#); [Hsieh et al., 1998b](#); [Zamanian et al., 2016](#)). Moreover their $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ signature improves our understanding of the hydrological cycles ([Horton et al., 2016](#)). With the Δ_{47} application the PC- $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ relationship can be further applied to determine the paleoaltimetry ([Quade et al., 2013](#); [Quade et al., 2007](#)).

I.G. Global and regional paleoenvironment during the Mid to Late Miocene transformation:

The Mid Miocene Climatic Optimum (MMCO) (*ca.* 17 – 13.8 Ma) event which had seen an above-modern temperature in mid-to-high latitudes ([Goldner et al., 2014](#)) and above modern CO_2 concentration ([Kürschner et al., 2008](#)) ended almost abruptly *ca.* 14.0 - 13.5 Ma ([Böhme, 2003](#)) with the beginning of Miocene cooling. This long term icehouse like condition which led profound environmental change in both terrestrial and marine ecosystems ([Holbourn et al., 2018](#)) had started with the growing Antarctic ice shield ~14 – 13 Ma ([Abreu and Anderson, 1998](#); [Tzanova et al., 2015](#); [Zachos et al., 2001](#)) and appearing of the Arctic or North hemisphere ice sheet ~12.6 Ma ([Fronval and Jansen, 1993](#); [Westerhold et al., 2005](#)); of this time frame 12.7 – 12.5 Ma and 11.0 – 10.8 Ma had significant stable ice volume ([Holbourn et al., 2013](#)). The Miocene cooling led to climatic zonation in Europe in between 12 – 10 Ma ([Böhme, 2003](#); [Böhme et al., 2008](#); [Böhme et al., 2011](#); [Mosbrugger et al., 2005](#)).

Under such background during the Middle to Late Miocene transition, ~11.6 Ma, the epicontinental Paratethys Sea was fragmented into a lake system (Lake Pannon) in the west and a strongly cut-off sea in the east of Europe ([Harzhauser et al., 2007](#)). Closer to the study site, the present day Irsee and HAM were belonged to the Western Paratethys realm in Central Europe (42 - 45°N paleolatitude) during 13 – 8 Ma with a prevalent subtropical climate ([Böhme, 2004](#)). The tectonic reorganization and Alpine orogeny perhaps had the greatest influence on the Eurasian humidity through increasing continentality ([Utescher et al., 2011](#)); being subtropical the South German Molasse Basin of the West-Central Paratethys realm at the Serravallian to Tortonian shift (~11.6 Ma) was warmer and marginally drier than today ([Böhme, 2003](#); [Böhme et al., 2008](#); [Böhme et al., 2011](#); [Bruch et al., 2006](#); [Bruch et al., 2011](#); [Mosbrugger et al., 2005](#)). The weakness in moisture carrying capacity of the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) in the continental Europe ([Böhme, 2004](#)) made the aridity to prevail in the Western Paratethys between ~13 – 11 Ma as supported by the piscine (Channidae), herpetological, and molluscan fossils ([Böhme, 2004](#); [Böhme et al., 2008](#); [Harzhauser et al., 2007](#); [Rostovtseva and Kuleshov, 2016](#)) alongside the paleofloristic observations ([Pound et al., 2012](#)). Although the timing of beginning of the drier climate is disputed ([Utescher et al., 2011](#)), the herpetofaunal and oceanographic data imply that this dry spell had intensified by the latest Middle Miocene ([Böhme et al., 2008](#); [De Boer et al., 2010](#)). The West-Central Paratethys realm experienced a mean annual temperature (MAT) ~14.5 – 15°C and mean annual precipitation (MAP) ~1050 – 1220 mm during the Serravallian to Tortonian transition according to paleobotanical indications ([Mosbrugger et al., 2005](#)) whereas the concomitant and herpetological records suggest much dryer conditions, with a MAP range between 450 mm to ~1200 mm ([Böhme et al., 2008](#)). However the estimation from mammalian fossils indicate a further increment of the MAP, upto ~1474 mm in this region for the earlier Late Miocene ([Fortelius et al., 2006](#)).

The Alpine uplift modulated the features of the adjacent land and ocean alike ([Kocsis et al., 2008](#)). Collapsing of marine connection to the Paratethys Sea made the Paratethys realm a hypersaline (~15 psu) and extremely evaporative estuarine environment likewise of rock pools or mudflats with oversaturated carbonate ([Harzhauser et al., 2007](#); [Latal et al., 2004](#); [Rostovtseva and Kuleshov, 2016](#)). The highly enriched $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values from the mollusks in the Western Paratethys (-3 to +1‰) during the early Pannonian (~11.4 – 11.0 Ma) ([Harzhauser](#)

[et al., 2007](#)), in the Central Paratethys (~ -4.5‰) during the Upper Sarmatian/Lower Pannonian intersection (~11.61 Ma) ([Latal et al., 2004](#)), and in the Eastern Paratethys (1 to 2.4‰) during the end of Middle Sarmatian (~11 Ma) ([Rostovtseva and Kuleshov, 2016](#)) reflects this marginal marine background. A simultaneous $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ enrichment of -0.4 to +2.8‰ in the Western Paratethys during the early Pannonian (~11.4 – 11.0 Ma) reveals of a strongly alkaline (pH 9-10) Paratethys Sea ([Harzhauser et al., 2007](#)). However in the central Paratethys realm the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ was rather depleted (~ -9‰) in ~11.61 Ma ([Latal et al., 2004](#)); the depletion was synchronous with the global carbon maxima (CM) event — CM7 (11.45 Ma) ([Cooke et al., 2008](#)) which advocates high biological productivity in the water due to mass development of diatoms as result of multifactors inclusive the Miocene cooling from 13.2 - 6 Ma ([Rostovtseva and Kuleshov, 2016](#)).

The extreme glacial conditions (Mi event) by the long term astronomical variations which were corresponding to the Alpine orogeny had good impacts over the salinization and evaporation of the declined Paratethys domain. The Mi4 and Mi5 events which advanced succession of sea-level-fall as a result of Antarctic ice sheet enhancement ([Kocsis et al., 2008](#); [Miller et al., 1991](#)) were coincided with the latest Middle to early Late Miocene however placing them in right sequence is challenging. The Mi4 which was concomitant with the Eastern Antarctica ice sheet expansion ([Cooke et al., 2008](#)) could occur at ~12.2Ma ([Lourens and Hilgen, 1997](#)) or 12.56 Ma ([Cooke et al., 2008](#)) or 13.2 Ma ([Westerhold et al., 2005](#)). The Mi5 (11.57 Ma) which was concurrent with the Western Antarctica Ice sheet accumulation ([Cooke et al., 2008](#)) is positioned at the base of chron C5r at ~11.7 Ma ([Miller et al., 1991](#); [Westerhold et al., 2005](#)). However in the Mediterranean it appeared at ~11.4 Ma ([Turco et al., 2001](#)). The latest observation is in view of that the Mi5 consisted of 3 to 4 maxima with an average duration of 100 kyr from 11.8 to 11.4 Ma of which the cooling amplitude was possibly at low in 11.4 Ma and high at 11.7 Ma ([Westerhold et al., 2005](#)).

The primary moisture source of modern precipitation in Germany is the Atlantic Ocean and not the Mediterranean Sea ([Sodemann and Zubler, 2010](#); [Stumpp et al., 2014](#)) where the latter contains more depleted $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ than the former ([Araguás-Araguás et al., 2000](#); [Stumpp et al., 2014](#)). This seems to be effective since the disintegration of the Paratethys and so here is an outline on the fluctuating oceanic sources of the Parathethys realm since latest

Middle Miocene. The $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ signature implies a well connection between the Mediterranean with the global oceans (the Atlantic and the Indian) from 13 to 8 Ma; furthermore the ϵNd indicates the oscillatory inputs of the Indian Ocean (13 Ma), the Atlantic Ocean (12–11 Ma) and locally evolved seawater (Paratethys) in the Mediterranean. ([Kocsis et al., 2008](#)).

Meanwhile the Atlantic inflow which was contemporaneous with Mi5 cooling probably had begun by a short sea rise ([Kocsis et al., 2008](#); [Miller et al., 2005](#); [Miller et al., 1991](#); [Westerhold et al., 2005](#)) when there was a small scale global warming ([Harzhauser et al., 2007](#); [Zachos et al., 2001](#)) and reached to climax at a lowered global sea level during the crest of the Mi5 event ([Kocsis et al., 2008](#)). The observation is in harmony with the seawater Mg/Ca records which suggest rising of temperature ($\sim 3^\circ\text{C}$ at 11.5 Ma to $\sim 6^\circ\text{C}$ at 10 Ma) of the Atlantic Bottom Water in the Serravallian to Tortonian interface ([Lear et al., 2003](#)). An underwater seismicity along the western margin of the North Atlantic Ocean (13- 10 Ma) ([Lear et al., 2003](#)) had possibly curbed the Atlantic–Pacific surface water exchange from 10.89 - 8.29 Ma as evidenced by the dissimilar coccolithophores on either side of the Central American Seaway (CAS) and might cause warming of the northern Atlantic and shift hydrological cycle in the Paratethys realm ([Böhme et al., 2008](#)) around the early Late Miocene. The observed $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ depletion in the North Atlantic after ~ 11.6 Ma ([Cramer et al., 2009](#)) also reflects the growing temperature in the Atlantic at the Mid Miocene/Late Miocene boundary. The events both on land and water thus made Paratethys realm warm and dry likewise of a subtropical climate with low humidity and high productivity ([Harzhauser et al., 2007](#); [Piller and Harzhauser, 2005](#)).

As a consequence, after its evolution in the Oligocene ([Fox et al., 2012](#); [Sage, 2004](#)) the C4 grass became abundant from the latest Late Miocene on global scale because of increased aridity ([Bruch et al., 2011](#); [Cerling et al., 1997](#); [Fox et al., 2012](#); [Herbert et al., 2016](#); [Passey et al., 2002](#)); however the dwindled Paratethys and expanding continentality may develop grassland in the Central Europe earlier during the Late Miocene ([Ivanov et al., 2011](#); [Utescher et al., 2011](#)). The oldest definite C4-grass ecosystems from Europe are recoded, based on phytolith proxy data, from the Tortonian-Messinian transition (7.4-7.1 Ma) of southern Europe ([Böhme et al., 2011](#)). The $p\text{CO}_2$ below 350 ppm is considered as threshold value that favour C4 over C3 plants ([Goldner et al., 2014](#)). Hence the Neogene $p\text{CO}_2$ shift

~260 - 220 ppmV concurrent of 12.2 - 11.2 Ma ([Pagani et al., 1999](#)) was in favour of C4 profusion ([Cerling et al., 1997](#); [Ehleringer et al., 1997](#); [Mosbrugger et al., 2005](#); [Sage, 2004](#)). However the range was later modified to upto 300 ppmV ([Pagani et al., 2005](#)) and the more recent alkenone- $p\text{CO}_2$ reconstruction indicated 300 – 480 ppmV for the concerned temporal scale ([Zhang et al., 2013](#)). But as the C4 adaptation is the resultant of multifactors that boosts photorespiration and cuts excess carbon ([Sage, 2004](#)) therefore even a higher $p\text{CO}_2$ was not a restriction for the C4 vegetation development in the Miocene that supported evolution of hypsodonty, large body size and bipedalism among the terrestrial mammals by end of the Mid Miocene ([Menéndez et al., 2017](#); [Moyà-Solà et al., 2009](#); [Nakatsukasa, 2004](#); [Uno et al., 2016](#); [Wang et al., 1994](#)). The geological timescale of the study area ~12.2 to 11.1 Ma ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)) that covers the transition phase from the Mid Miocene to the Late Miocene (~11.61 Ma) hence has good potential that holds the explanation of the changes in climate and biological features of the concerned ecosystems [Fig.4].

Figure 4: Cenozoic time scale where light green area indicates the timeframe of the present study. (adapted from <https://skepticalscience.com/print.php?n=2845>)

II. GEOGRAPHICAL AND GEOLOGICAL INFORMATION

II.A. Geographical information of sampling sites: Pedogenic carbonate samples were collected from the clay pit at Hammerschmiede and drill-core of Irsee. Both locations are situated in the eastern Allgäu region of southwestern Bavaria ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)) [Fig.5]. Hammerschmiede clay pit which is about 300 m west of the settlement Hammerschmiede / Pforzen and 4 km away from the north-west of Kaufbeuren ([Fuss et al., 2015](#)), situated at hillside base of western margin of the Wertach valley ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)). In the year 2011, the drilling task at Irsee was taken place at a plateau ~2 km west of the Church of Irsee village. The Irsee drill site is 4.3 km apart from the southwest of the Hammerschmiede clay pit ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)) [Fig.5]. Around 150.5 m drill-core is now stored at the sediment core repository of the Geoscience department, Tübingen University in Sand Drosselweg.

Figure 5: Topographical and geographical and Map of the study area. ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#))

II.B. Geological setting of the sampling sites: Geochronological origin of the sampling points lies between the Middle to the Late Miocene boundary which is equivalent to the base of the Tortonian stage 11.625 Ma ([Hüsing et al., 2007](#)) and it coincides with Hipparion datum ([Bernor et al., 1988](#)). However influence of the Late Miocene is more prominent ([Böhme, 2017](#)) in the Hammerschmiede section. But as it is considered that the terrestrial fossils are not the suitable option to define the Middle-to-Late Miocene boundary in European continental settings so it needs reference nearest to base of the Tortonian age; the North Alpine Foreland Basin (NAFB / Molasse basin) which comprises of the Oligocene and Miocene molasse sediments fulfills this requirement ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)). The NAFB is about 1000 km long and 10 - 200 km wide depression along northern margin of the Alpine mountain belt, extending from Lake Geneva from the west to the eastern end of the Alps near Vienna ([Rocholl et al., 2018](#)) [Fig.6]. It contains 30 Ma old continental as well as marine and brackish sediments deposits of the Oligocene and the Miocene as a result of foreland flexure during the Alpine orogeny ([Rocholl et al., 2018](#)).

Figure 6: Schematic paleogeographic map of the North Alpine Foreland Basin (NAFB) with direction of Middle Miocene sediment transport [black arrows] and areas with prevailing erosion [white] and sedimentation [yellow]. ([Rocholl et al., 2018](#))

The subsequent separation of the Atlantic Ocean from the world Ocean, formation of the Neotethys, increasing Alpine thrust aided in creation of the Molasse basin ([Böhme, 2017](#)). First sedimentation of the Molasse basin was marine origin of the Eastern Paratethys; then

~28 Ma marine to continental sediment transformation was started ([Böhme, 2017](#)). The youngest sedimentary deposition of the Molasse basin consists of clastic, fluvial to limnic sediments of the Middle Miocene Upper Freshwater Molasse ([Rocholl et al., 2018](#)). The Molasse tuffs represent acidic ashes derived from the Carpathian–Pannonian region ([Unger et al., 1990](#)), which was part of the central Paratethys during the Middle Miocene. The formation of the basin reflects the bending of the European plate under the tectonic pressure of the evolving Alps ([Homewood et al., 1986](#); [Schlunegger et al., 1997](#)). On account of two sedimentary cycles the ~4 km thick Molasse basin is subdivided into two subunits — Lower Marine (sand) / Freshwater (clay) Molasse [German:Untere Meeresmolasse / Untere Süßwassermolasse, (UMM/USM)] and the Upper Marine (sand) / Freshwater (clay) Molasse [German: Obere Meeresmolasse / Obere Süßwassermolasse], (OMM/OSM(UFM) ([Rocholl et al., 2018](#)).

Figure 7: Paleogeographic map of the Paratethys region during the late Early Badenian [ca. 15–14 Ma] with the location of sampled sites [black triangles], reference sites [red squares] and large calkalinic silicic volcanic centers [orange stars: BVK Bükkalja volcanic field, Hungary, GM Gutâi Mountains, Romania. 1 Bischofszell, 2 Heilsberg, 3 Krumbad, 4 Laimering, 5 Unterneul, 6 Zahling, 7 Hachelstuhl, 8 Ponholz]. ([Rocholl et al., 2018](#))

The UFM which consists of sand, gravel and clay formed when the river system had developed ~15 - 17 Ma in the eastern Alps. With the beginning of the Middle Miocene, ~16.3 Ma the UFM formed when the marine Molasse Sea had complete recreation from the western part of the Molasse basin ([Reichenbacher et al., 2013](#)) which led to sedimentation of alluvial fan along southern rim of this basin and a predominantly fluvial sedimentation along the basin axis ([Rocholl et al., 2018](#)). Constituent volcanic ashes of this basin were from

the Parathethys which had base ~5 km at below, for example in and around the present day Hungary ([Böhme, 2017, 2018](#); [Rocholl et al., 2018](#)) [Fig.7]. The Hammerschmiede clay pit belongs to the youngest part of the “Upper Series” in the central NAFB ([Doppler, 1989](#); [Fuss et al., 2015](#)). The nearby Irsee village and monastery ends ~100 m higher than the base of the Hammerschmiede clay pit ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)) and lithostratigraphically the Irsee also belongs to part of the UFM [Fig.8] ([Doppler, 1989](#)).

Figure 8: Location of Molasse Basin and terrestrial deposits of the Upper Freshwater Molasse (UFM) in Germany. UFM without pebbles (Light grey), UFM with pebbles (Medium grey), UFM without pebbles but with coal and humus (Dark grey), main drainage and side tributaries (Black arrows). ([Eronen and Rössner, 2007](#))

Figure 9: Irsee drill-core lithology with topographic label (left) and height label below the surface (right). Hammerschmiede lithology with height label below the surface (right) and sampling points (left). The correlation of Irsee & HAM is shown with dotted lines. On top with topographic map of the locations and cross section ranging from the Irsee drill-core to the HAM clay pit are shown. [after(Kirscher et al., 2016)]

II.C. Lithological description of Hammerschmiede (HAM): Thick floodplain (~20 m) deposits of clays, marls and sandstones from the UFM have constituted the HAM outcrop [Fig.10A]. At its base there is a developed coal bed while a few thin coal layers are located around its top [Fig.10B] ([Fuss et al., 2015](#)). The horizontal sediment beds are usually bright-grey in color, fine-grained (clay to fine sand fractions) [Fig.10C], carbonated and have distinct pedogenic overprints [Fig.10D] ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)). The HAM clay pit has three traditional fossil-bearing layers which are known as HAM 1, 2 and 3 ([Fuss et al., 2015](#)). A fourth layer (HAM4) primarily having small vertebrates and well-preserved unionid bivalves was excavated in the recent times ([Fuss et al., 2015](#); [Schneider and Prieto, 2011](#)).

Figure 10: A) Outcrop of the HAM claypit. B) Prominent coal layer of HAM outcrop. C) UFM sediment clusters around carbonate concretions in HAM. D) Pedogenic carbonates in a HAM sampling point.

In addition there is a newly discovered fifth layer (HAM5) which has several precious vertebrate fossils including hominoid remnants ([Böhme, 2017, 2018](#); [Fuss et al., 2015](#); [Kirscher et al., 2016](#)). The east-west directed HAM5 paleochannel [Fig.11] is rich with silty clay and pedogenic CO_3^{2-} as a consequence of subhumid and semiarid conditions; the paleochannel was a part of south to north flowing large braided river system and perhaps was linked with the oldest known plaeofluvial system of the Danube river ([Böhme, 2017, 2018](#)).

Figure 11: HAM5 paleochannel and fossil excavation site.

Semi-allochthonous deposition of the fossils in the channel sediments and lesser abrasion marks on the fossils are not in favour of long-distance fossil transportation in HAM. Moreover presence of fine sand, silt and clay suggests the transport as non-destructive due to the low-energy-rivulet flow ([Fuss et al., 2015](#)). The comprehensive lithological information [Fig.9] of the six sampling sites from the Ham clay pit is described in Appendix-1.

II.D. Lithological description of Irsee drill-core: The total depth of the Irsee drill-core includes all of the HAM section is 150.5 m [Fig.9]; its sectional thickness that covers the HAM clay pit is ~50 m ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)). The Pleistocene till and gravel coverage diminishes the reachable molasse sediments to 122 m ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)). About 75% of the molasse core consists of primarily grey, fine-grained silts besides sandy or clayey marls while 25% of the molasse sequence consists of sands or sandy silts without a clay fraction ([Kirscher et al.,](#)

[2016](#)). Pedogenic carbonate concretions and soft calcitic precipitates present throughout the drill-core but in the deeper parts marls are relatively cemented ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)) [Fig.12 (A-B)].

Figure 12: A) Deeper sections of Irsee drill-core with more carbonate concretions (blue arrow). B) Upper sections of Irsee drill-core section with lesser carbonate concretions (blue arrow) & soft sandstones (yellow arrow).

The marly facies are interrupted by ~20 decalcified clayey to silty horizontal remains of preceding weathered surfaces; moreover the decalcified strata are often characterized by increased organic contents (blackish, humic layers) and have culminated in three small lignite seams at 42.35–42.50 m, 43.60–43.90 m and 84.87– 85.12 m depth of the drill-core ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)). Sandstones related with river channel were not identified in the drill-core ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)) except some portions of the top core beneath the Pliocene deposits. The depositional sequence of these sediments points out existence of an extensive floodplain ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)). The comprehensive lithological information [Fig.9] of the twenty-four sampling points from the Irsee drill-core is described in Appendix-2.

III. METHODOLOGY

III.A. Sample Collection: Sediment samples contained the pedogenic carbonate concretions from Hammerschmiede clay pit and Irsee drill-core were collected using sharp knives, hammer, and brushes [Fig.13]. During the sample collection from the drill-core, water was splashed a little bit over the dried parts to visualize the carbonate assemblages clearly.

Figure 13: A) Pedogenic carbonate nodules from the Hammerschmiede clay pit. B) Pedogenic carbonate nodule bearing Irsee drill-core.

The collected sediment chunks were put into plastic ziplocks with appropriate numbering and taken back to the sediment preparation laboratory of the Tübingen University. To relax the attachment between the carbonate nodules and the sediment mounds, the samples were soaked well in warm water in plastic tubs for two consecutive days in the laboratory; the tubs were covered with lids to avoid contamination. Some sediment chunks were very hard to dissolve; in those cases water was changed after a day.

III.B. Sample preparation:

III.B.1. Water screening: Afterwards the wet samples were strained out with a sieve having 700 μm mesh size under moderate warm water flow [Fig.14]. Due to the fragile nature of the carbonate clusters no mechanical force was applied during the water screening. The carbonate particles were handpicked from the sieve and kept in 50mL. polypropylene falcon tubes (RFF – N64.1) [Fig.15 (A-C)].

Figure 14: Water screening of the sample.

Figure 15: A) Pedogenic carbonate nodules. B) Handpicked waterscreened pedogenic carbonates. C) Transferring of handpicked pedogenic carbonates to the falcon tube.

In order to dissolve finer sediment around the surface of the carbonate particles further, the falcon tubes were then filled in with mild warm water and shook gently. The consequent murky water of the falcon tubes was then decanted through a finer sieve to avoid the loss of the carbonate particles [Fig.16 (A-C)]. The process was repeated twice for better output. The finally cleaned samples were slanted on the test-tube racks [Fig.17].

Figure 16: A) Dissolved sediment in warm water. B) Water screening of the sample with finer mesh. C) Washed carbonate nodules. D) Pedogenic carbonates after final water screening.

Figure 17: Carbonate nodules after final wash.

III.B.2. Oven drying: The isolated carbonates were oven dried at $\sim 53^{\circ}\text{C}$ for two nights in the Memmert oven, [Loading Model 108-800, P. O. Box 1720, D91107 Schwabach] [Fig.18].

During the oven drying, the falcon tubes were covered with paper plug in place of their mouth-caps to allow air flow as well as avoid contamination [Fig.19A]. After drying they mostly look like off-white amorphous nodules of varied size [Fig.19B]

Figure 18: Memmert oven.

Figure 19: A) Oven drying of samples with paper plug (yellow arrow). B) Oven dried carbonate nodules.

III.B.3. Grinding: The oven-dried pedogenic carbonates were grinded into fine powder with an agate mortar and pestle [Fig.20A]. The carbonate powder was then transferred and kept in properly labeled eppendorf tubes [Fig.20 (B-D)]. Before grinding task of a sampling point the tools were wiped with acetone to avoid contamination from the residues of the precedent sampling point. There were total 30 samples of which 24 belonged to the Irsee sediment drill-core and the remaining 6 were from the Hammerschmiede clay pit [Fig.20D].

Figure 20: A) Grinding of carbonate nodules. B) Scrapping of carbonate powders with clean incisors. C) Carbonate powder in paper boat for transferring to eppendorf tube. D) Eppendorf tubes with carbonate powder.

III.C. Isotope Analysis: The isotope analysis ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ & $\delta^{18}\text{O}$) of the carbonate was based on accepted principles ([Achyuthan et al., 2007](#); [McCrea, 1950](#)). The task was done in Gas-IRMS at the Erlangen University. The powder samples were turned into CO_2 with adding ortho phosphoric acid (H_3PO_4). The results are reported as δ (‰) relative to PDB scale ([Achyuthan et al., 2007](#); [Leone et al., 2000](#)).

IV. RESULT

IV.A. Stratigraphic unit nomenclature: The isotopic information of the Irsee and the HAM area are discussed collectively because of the spatial proximity (~4km) of the sampling stations. Besides the overall reading of isotopic values, the results are also interpreted under three separate temporal dimensions which are 12.207 – 12.013 Ma, 11.685 – 11.598 Ma and 11.354 – 11.154 Ma. According to the Geological scale these sequential units are ascribed to Middle Serravallian (12.207 – 12.013 Ma; = late Early Sarmatian of Central Paratethys, = late Volhynian / Early Bessarabian of Eastern Paratethys), Late Serravallian (11.685 – 11.641 Ma; = latest Sarmatian of Central Paratethys, = late Early Bessarabian of Eastern Paratethys), and Early Tortonian (11.620 – 11.154 Ma; = earliest Pannonian of Central Paratethys, = early Middle Bessarabian of Eastern Paratethys) respectively.

Figure 21: Age clustering of the sampling site. ELM- Early Late Miocene; LLM-Late Middle Miocene; MMM- Mid Middle Miocene; EH1- Younger erosion hiatus; EH2- Older erosion hiatus.

Two major gaps which have eroded the region's stratigraphic continuance ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)) are obvious in this observation too. The older erosion EH1 (~ 300 kyrs gap) of about 45 m of sediment occurred in the upper Serravallian (upper Sarmatian) between 12.2 Ma -

11.7 Ma whereas the younger erosion EH2 (~ 150 kyrs gap) of about 27 m of sediment took place in the lower Tortonian (earliest Pannonian) between 11.59 - 11.44 Ma ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)). The stratigraphic hiatuses are also evident in this present study. Hence in resemblance with the erosional sequence, the age cluster of this study is named as Mid Middle Miocene (MMM) 12.207 – 12.013 Ma, Late Middle Miocene (LMM) 11.685 – 11.598 Ma, and Early Late Miocene (ELM) 11.354 – 11.154 Ma [Fig.21]. Due to magnetostratigraphic correlation of core to outcrop profiles ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)) the HAM outcrop sampling points are grouped with the LMM section of the Irsee profile.

IV.B. Isotope data: The Irsee drill core $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ has a range from -10.90‰ to -4.01‰ while that of the HAM outcrop is -10.22‰ to -8.00‰ [Fig.22]. On the other hand $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of the Irsee drill core has a range from -7.21‰ to -4.74‰ while that of the HAM outcrop is -5.99‰ to -5.71‰ [Fig.23]. The data are available in Appendix-3. Interestingly extreme nature of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ enrichment and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ depletion, likewise of an outlier, is observed at 51.60 mbs of the Irsee drill core which is coeval of 11.222 Ma. In the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ profile another outlier consisting of the extreme enriched value is observed corresponding to 100.50 mbs of the Irsee drill core at 11.661 Ma.

Figure 22: Temporal d¹³C variation in Irsee and HAM.

Figure 23: Temporal $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ variation in Irsee and HAM.

Inclusive of all the readings, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ has a mean value of -9.07‰ while the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ mean value is -5.95‰ ; on temporal scale, the mean values of both variables have changed noticeably. For the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ there is a gradual enrichment of its mean towards the younger profiles, from the MMM to ELM whereas the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ mean has a fluctuation in which the most enriched crest is at the middle section (LMM) while the depleted troughs are at the two ends (ELM and MMM) of the profile — however likewise of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$, the most depleted $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ is observed in the oldest time span. The data are provided in [Table 1].

Table 1: Summarized data of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ & $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values from the entire profile

Section	Entire Range	ELM	LMM	MMM
Number of Samples	30	9	12	9
$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰)				
Max	-4.01	-4.01	-7.78	-8.66
Mean	-9.07	-8.18	-9.23	-9.74
Min	-10.90	-10.50	-10.47	-10.90
$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰)				
Max	-4.74	-5.34	-4.74	-5.78
Mean	-5.95	-5.99	-5.66	-6.30
Min	-7.21	-7.21	-5.99	-6.99

IV.C. Statistical relationship of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (R^2 and R): The figured out variance in dependent variable ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) in response with independent variable ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$) is $\sim 5\%$ ($R^2 = 0.054$) and the two variables has a negative correlation ($R = -0.229$). Consideration of the sampling point at 11.222 Ma as an outlier weakens the coefficient of determination to $\sim 2\%$ ($R^2 = 0.023$) although the respective correlation ($R = 0.151$) improves. Likewise consideration of the sampling point at 11.661 Ma as an outlier is weakening the coefficient of determination further to $\sim 0.3\%$ ($R^2 = 0.003$) and although respective correlation is not improved much ($R = 0.059$). These findings have made the outlier assumption critical. Henceforth the coefficient of the determination and correlation of the individual temporal clusters are also measured.

Figure 24: Correlation plots between the d13C and d¹⁸O.
[ELM – Early Late Miocene; LMM- Late Middle Miocene; MMM- Mid Middle Miocene.]

At the ELM section, the variance of dependent variable ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) and independent variable ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$) is $\sim 58\%$ ($R^2 = 0.576$) and their correlation is negative ($R = -0.759$). While consideration of the sampling point at 11.222 Ma as an outlier is highly subsiding the coefficient of determination to $\sim 7\%$ ($R^2 = 0.068$) but the negativity of their correlation has improved ($R = -0.261$). At the LMM section, the variance of dependent variable ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) and independent

variable ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$) is ~19% ($R^2= 0.186$) and the variables are positively correlated ($R= 0.431$). While the consideration of the sampling point at 11.661 Ma as an outlier is highly weakening the coefficient of determination to ~5% ($R^2= 0.054$) but the positivity of their correlation has declined ($R= 0.233$). At the MMM section, the variance of dependent variable ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) and independent variable ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$) is ~11% ($R^2= 0.113$) but the variables are negatively correlated ($R= -0.336$). Hence the sequential observations too are not fortifying the outlier assumptions. For understanding the significance among the mean difference of the isotopic values of three age clusters one way type III Anova is performed in R software.

IV.C.1. ANOVA Output: The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ among the three age clusters is found to differ significantly ($F=3.606$, $df=2,27$, $p=0.041$). Tukey posthoc test 'hsd' and 'Bonferroni adjustment' has indicated that the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value of the ELM is significantly higher than the MMM ($t=2.62$, $df=27$, $p=0.043$) [Fig.25A]. The $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ among the three age clusters is also found to differ significantly ($F=5.435$, $df=2,27$, $p=0.01$). Tukey posthoc test 'hsd' and 'Bonferroni adjustment' indicate that the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value of the LMM is significantly higher than the MMM ($t=3.29$, $df=27$, $p=0.009$) [Fig.25B].

Figure 25: ANOVA output of the entire profile; A) Carbon isotope. B) Oxygen isotope.

IV.C.2. Outlier assumption: However consideration of the aforesaid outlier at 11.222 Ma modifies the ANOVA outputs. For the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ there is no longer significant difference among

the age clusters ($F= 2.530$, $df =2,26$, $p=0.1$) [Fig.26A]. Whereas the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ among the three age clusters is found to differ highly significantly ($F=7.829$, $df=2, 26$, $p=0.002$); in the MMM $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values were significantly lower than the ELM and LMM (Tukey-test with Bonferroni p-value adjustment; ELM vs. MMM: $t=2.60$, $df=26$, $p=0.046$; LMM vs. MMM: $t=3.90$, $df=26$, $p=0.002$) [Fig.26B].

Figure 26: ANOVA output of the entire profile without 11.222 Ma data; A) Carbon Isotope. B) Oxygen isotope.

Figure 27: ANOVA output of the entire profile without 11.222 Ma & 11.661 Ma data; A) Carbon Isotope. B) Oxygen isotope.

Similarly consideration of the aforesaid outlier at 11.661 Ma modifies the ANOVA outputs. For the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ there is again no longer significant difference among the age clusters ($F= 2.587$, $df =2,25$, $p=0.1$) [Fig.27A]. Whereas the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ among the three age clusters is found to differ highly significantly ($F=7.857$, $df=2,25$, $p=0.002$). In the MMM $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values were significantly lower than the ELM and LMM (Tukey-test with Bonferroni p-value adjustment; ELM vs. MMM: $t=2.95$, $df=25$, $p=0.020$; LMM vs. MMM: $t=3.78$, $df=25$, $p=0.002$) [Fig.27B]. The ANOVA outputs henceforth are not in favour of any outlier assumption in this observation.

IV.D. Interpretation of C3 and C4 components (%): The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of the pedogenic carbonates are useful information for determining the percentage (%) of the C3 and C4 components of the concerned paleovegetation ([Han et al., 1997](#)). Hence after ([Wang and Zheng, 1989](#)) percentage of the C3 and C4 flora in the studied profile has been calculated [Appendix-4]. The mean value informs that with the growing age profile, the C3% has ascended while the opposite is observed for the C4%. Removing the data coeval of 11.222 Ma, has just enhanced the respective C3% and C4% otherwise there is no change in their temporal relationship [Table 2]. This measurement is also not in view of considering the data from 11.222 Ma as an outlier. The percentage profile of the C3 and C4 vegetation is shown in [Fig. 28].

Table 2: Summarisation of the C3 and C4 vegetation in percentage from the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{PC}}$ values.

Section	C3%			C4%		
	Max	Mean	Min	Max	Mean	Min
Entire Range	93.00	79.80	44.00	56.00	20.20	7.00
Entire Range without outlier	93.00	81.03	67.00	33.00	18.97	7.00
ELM	81.03	73.44	44.00	56.00	26.56	10.00
ELM without outlier	90.00	77.12	67.00	33.00	22.88	10.00
LMM	90.00	80.92	71.00	29.00	19.08	10.00
MMM	93.00	84.67	77.00	23.00	15.33	7.00

Figure 28: C4% in the paleovegetation of the entire profile.

IV.E. Disparity of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ profile: Throughout the entire reading it has been observed that there are five sections where the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values are incongruent i.e. simultaneous occurrence of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ enrichment and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ depletion [Fig.29].

Figure 29: Incongruity zones between the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values.

The major incongruence zone (IC1) comprises of the sampling points from 42.80 to 54.20 mbs of the ELM profile. The next incongruent zone (IC2) comprises of sampling points 71.20 to 85.40 mbs. At the sampling point 97.50 mbs there is the tiniest incongruity (IC3) among

the entire profile. However it is to be noted that the IC3 zone at 11.620 Ma contained reworked samples and so these carbonates are reflecting paleoenvironment of some older timescale and not the HAM5 channel. The widest area of incongruence (IC4) starts from the last point of LMM (104.80 mbs) and continues to the initial four points of the MMM (108.40 - 124.50 mbs). And the last irregularity (IC5) is observed at the sampling point 138.70 mbs of the MMM profile. Henceforth the amplitude of the disparity between the two variables is the sharpest in the youngest profile while it has the least presence in the LMM profile; and the highest disparity frequency is observed in the oldest profile although the amplitude is the smallest at here.

V. DISCUSSION

V.A. Paleoenvironmental signature of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ cross-plot: The cross correlation of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values from the oldest profile has a weak covariant trend while that of the middle and the youngest profile are widely scattered [Fig.30]. Henceforth it can be assumed that the studied pedogenic carbonates had not undergone any major diagenetic recrystallisation underneath the soil otherwise the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values would become more homogeneous ([Cojan et al., 2013](#); [Lohmann, 1988](#)).

Figure 30: Correlation plots between the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$.
ELM – Early Late Miocene; LMM – Late Middle Miocene; MMM – Mid Middle Miocene.

Excluding the MMM section the scattered features are also suggestive of poor linking of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ enrichment in the remaining sections ([Volk et al., 2011](#)). Contrarily for the same reason evaporation and photosynthesis had no strong independence ([Léveillé et al., 2007](#); [Volk et al., 2011](#)) at the MMM section unlike of the following younger sections. The individual homogeneous distribution of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and also the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ implies absence of major

interference on the carbonate crystallization process in the respective sections [Fig.31 (A-B)].

Figure 31: A) Normal Q-Q Plot for $d^{13}C$ data. B) Normal Q-Q Plot for $d^{18}O$.

The variability in oxidation levels of paleoriver channel and its floodplain was one of the regulating factors of the paleosol oxygen concentration of Irsee and HAM which is reflected in their $\delta^{18}O_{PC}$. Due to higher soil respiration and weaker evaporation, in the humid regions the $\delta^{13}C_{PC}$ values are highly depleted ($\sim -14\%$) than the semiarid and arid regions ([Cerling, 1984](#); [Cojan et al., 2013](#); [Ghosh et al., 1995](#)); the most depleted value of the entire range at 12.106 Ma of the MMM is above the threshold value. The physical observation has disclosed that the ELM profile which represents a rather unsteady landscape which may hold a reason of extreme shift of its isotopic values.

V.B. Understanding the $\delta^{13}C_{PC}$ based paleoecosystem: The $\delta^{13}C$ estimation from the MMM and the LMM sections varies between -10.90% to -7.78% while at the ELM profile the enrichment reaches upto -4.01% . The mean $\delta^{13}C$ estimation of the entire 1.05 Myr range as well as of the three temporal sections is below the threshold value (-8%) of significant moisture stress and existence of the C4 vegetation ([Latorre et al., 1997](#)) [Fig.32]. The $\delta^{13}C[CO_2]_{atm}$ of the Early Miocene and the Middle Miocene were 0.4% and 1.3% more enriched than the preindustrial value ([Cojan et al., 2013](#); [Tippie et al., 2010](#)); henceforth the resultant $\delta^{13}C$ upper limit of typical C3 vegetation were -8.6% (Early Miocene) and -7.7% (Mid Miocene) respectively. Whereas the Late Miocene $\delta^{13}C[CO_2]_{atm}$ was within the

preindustrial range, precisely $\sim -6.0\text{‰}$ (Tippie et al., 2010) and hence $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ upper limit of typical C3 vegetation of the Late Miocene was -8.5‰ . These figures have been reported as -7.9‰ (12.49 -12.0 Ma) and -8.0‰ (11.99 – 11.00 Ma) in another observation (Passey et al., 2009). Thus the mean $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the entire profile of this study is within the usual preindustrial C3 vegetation index (Cojan et al., 2013; Passey et al., 2009; Tippie and Pagani, 2007).

Figure 32: The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ profile of the study site from the Mid to Late Miocene transition. The C3 upper limit of the respective temporal scale is considered after B. J. Tippie et al., 2010 and I. Cojan et al., 2013. The pink area represents benthic $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ based average $\delta^{13}\text{C}[\text{CO}_2]_{\text{atm}}$ 12.9 – 7.9 Ma after B.J. Tippie et al, 2010.

The sectional mean $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values suggest that the paleovegetation of LMM and MMM sections [Table1 of Result section] was remained within the Middle Miocene C3 vegetation province although with the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ enrichment of -7.78‰ at 11.676 Ma and -8.00‰ at 11.620 Ma the relationship was marginal. The mean $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the ELM infers that it had marginally

crossed the threshold level of estimated Late Miocene C3 vegetation domain and contained C4 components. Conversely the heaviest $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value (-4.01‰) at the ELM profile is lower than extreme $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{PC-C3}}$ level ($\sim -3\text{‰}$) of the arid environment ([Amundson et al., 1988](#); [Cojan et al., 2013](#)); Furthermore the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ data of the entire profile are not supporting presence of humid soils ([Cerling et al., 1989](#); [Cojan et al., 2013](#); [Quade et al., 1989](#)). Hence paleoecosystem of the ELM was semiarid that had faced with some moisture stress which seems to be acute at 11.222 Ma. However the value is marginally below the isotopic benchmarks of the concerned $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{PC-C4}}$ dominance ([Passey et al., 2009](#)).

Figure 33: The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ distribution during the Late Middle Miocene in Irsee and HAM.

The interactive signature of the sampling points from Irsee and HAM [Fig.33] points out that except for the 11.620 Ma span (IC3 zone), the HAM site had more C3 abundance than the Irsee site however towards the youngest upper sections, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of both sites had a convergent depletion trend. The variation in the lower parts of the interactive curve which all together belong to the LMM profile seems to have no understandable explanation other than the climatic modification in local scale such as more humidity in the HAM region than Irsee during the LMM.

V.B.1. Paleobiomass percentage: Overall a dominant percentage of the C3 plants were observed throughout this study which had lessened with the decreasing time scale [Table 2,

Fig. 8 of Result section] and this trend had paved the way for the C4 vegetation proliferation. However as the interpretation is supposed to base on average preindustrial $d^{13}C[CO_2]_{atm}$ hence the raw data were run under two separate refined models [Fig.34].

Figure 34: C4 contribution (%) in the paleovegetation of Irsee and Hammerschmiede after three different Neogene $\delta^{13}C$ time series models. Red dashed line represents the significant level of the C4 contribution.

According to the model by B.H Passey et al, 2009 [Appendix-4] despite the appearance of first signal at 11.676 Ma the C4 had no presence until the beginning of the ELM, 11.34 Ma. Even though the other model as mentioned by K. T. Uno et al, 2016 [Appendix-4] suggests no C4 signals until the ELM but it reveals a better amplitude of the C4 taxa in the ELM than the former model. In wider scale, since the Miocene, contribution of the C4 grasses on the local paleoecosystem has been approved when their abundance had become at least 20% (Edwards et al., 2010). In that sense the C4 contribution to the local paleoecosystem was significant only at 11.222 Ma.

V.B.2. Spatiotemporal comparison of $\delta^{13}C_{PC}$ in regional scale: The $\delta^{13}C$ range of this study is well related with the available maximum and minimum $\delta^{13}C$ data of the spatiotemporal periphery [Fig.35]. The enrichment of the Late Miocene (7.37 – 7.11 Ma) samples from the Mediterranean Greece (Böhme et al., 2017) may either represent the spreading C4 taxa

([Holbourn et al., 2018](#)) or reflect estuarine C3 taxa that are enriched than their terrestrial counterparts ([Choi et al., 2001](#)). The depleted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of the Middle Miocene Bavarian bentonites ([Köster and Gilg, 2015](#)) and the Early Holocene Groundwater in Munich ([Choi et al., 2001](#)) are suggestive of paleoecosystems with C3 vegetation dominance in the Molasse Basin during the time concerned and the information are in accordance with the global trends ([Sage, 2004](#); [Tippie and Pagani, 2007](#)). The present study which has more positive $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ than the Middle Miocene data ([Köster and Gilg, 2015](#)) signifies a declining C3 flora possibly for lesser moisture in the paleoecosystem concerned. The reading of this present work is closely comparable with $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ distribution in the Siwalik Himalaya, Pakistan (-9.73‰) ([Behrensmeyer et al., 2007](#); [Quade and Cerling, 1995](#)) but heavier than North America (-7.6‰) ([Fox et al., 2012](#)) during the Mid to Late Miocene transition.

Figure 35: Regional spatiotemporal $d^{13}\text{C}$ status in comparison with this study.

V.C. Account on the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PC}}$ based paleoclimate: The $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ had fluctuated from -4.74‰ to -7.21‰ throughout the observed temporal sections within the entire 1.05 Myr range [Fig.36]. It is of interest that the depletion level of no sampling points of the LMM had dropped below -6.00‰ and toying with this trend, *ca.* 11.66 Ma, the LMM profile contains the heaviest $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ signature (-4.74‰) of the entire reading. Henceforth the LMM section had

the warmest and/or driest phase in this study. On the other hand depleted $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values are frequent in the oldest and youngest temporal profiles which the order of mean $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values [Table 1 of Result section] is also reflecting. The highest depletion (-7.21‰) at 11.222 Ma is suggestive of having the wettest and/or coldest condition in upper end of the profile. However the assumption of the concomitant subtropical continental Europe ([Böhme et al., 2008](#)) and the global oceanic $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ pattern [Fig.36] is not apparently going on with this $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ assumption, particularly in the ELM profile. Hence it is not possible to delineate a threshold $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value, eg. -6.00‰, between the warm and cold condition for the present spatiotemporal range.

Figure 36: The $d^{18}\text{O}$ profile of the study site from the Mid to Late Miocene transition (Left). The synchronous $d^{18}\text{O}$ value of global ocean (Right) where the blue peaks are representing cooling phase and the red peaks are representing warming phase.

It can also be anticipated that other than temperature some other factors such as meteoric events could bring about overall 2.46‰ $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ oscillation in this observation. In fact this part of the Molasse basin had witnessed such occasion when at ~15 Ma, the Ries & Steinheim Impact took place; however as within next 100 yrs Southern Germany recovered from the impact effect ([Böhme et al., 2002](#)) so meteoric impact over the anomalous $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ cycle is dubious.

Figure 37: The $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ distribution during the Late Middle Miocene in Irsee and HAM.

The interactive feature [Fig.37] of the sampling points from Irsee and HAM implies that except for the 11.663 – 11.659 Ma span where the isotopic difference between the subsequent ages reached to ~1‰, the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ difference between the two sites were remain insignificant particularly at the younger phase. From this observation it may be inferred that continental effect was not a strong regulator of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ fluctuations in between the two sites as they are only ~4 km. apart. This assumption is against the earlier guess on the local climate governed $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ variation for this interactive range.

V.C.1. Paleoaltitude reconstruction from $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PC}}$: It has been estimated that the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of the precipitation decrement range is 1.6‰ to 4.1‰ per 1000 m ([Chamberlain and Poage, 2000](#); [Cojan et al., 2013](#); [Quade et al., 1989](#)) which becomes 0.16‰ to 0.41‰ per 100 m. Absence

of direct marine sediment in this profile allows looking into plaeoaltitude effect over $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ differences. The top most (34.30 mbs) and bottom most (146.20 mbs) sampling points which belonged to the time scale of 11.154 Ma and 12.207 Ma respectively have a $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PC}}$ variance of 0.43‰ over ~112 m elevation difference. This $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ variation as a reason of altitude difference is related with other paleoenvironmental observations as well as with the modern average altitude effect (0.47‰ per 100 m) in Germany ([Stumpp et al., 2014](#)) although the values of consecutive stations do not always corroborate the established views and this anomaly is more frequent in the youngest age cluster. Hence the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ variation cannot be simply referred as a consequence of paleoelevation effect; since the altitude of the entire profile was within 1000 m so much interpretation cannot be possible in this aspect.

V.C.2. Paleotemperature reconstruction from $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PC}}$: The polynomial relation between water and calcite ([Friedman and O'Neil, 1977](#); [O'Neil et al., 1969](#)) is closely effective in marine environment ([Tanner, 2010](#)). The $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{Precipitation}}$ of present-day is not sufficient for the paleotemperature quantification ([Ryskov et al., 2008](#)). Therefore $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PC}}$ cannot estimate paleotemperature in conventional isotope studies ([Koch, 1998](#)). In addition the pedogenic carbonate is enriched by 2–10‰ compare to calcite in equilibrium with meteoric water because of the evaporative enrichment of soil water ([Cerling and Quade, 1993](#)). Hence the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PC}}$ output of this study rather only suggests paleoenvironmental difference over temporal scale and not the give the exact paleotemperature figure.

V.C.3. Spatiotemporal comparison of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PC}}$ in regional scale: When comparing with the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values from other sources [Fig.38] it is observed that the magnitude of difference between this study and the adjacent era has been reduced unlike of the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$. Although the minimum $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PC}}$ reading of this study is lower than that of the Late Miocene (7.37 – 7.11 Ma) ([Böhme et al., 2017](#)) but being a coastal site the amount effect might be more pronounced in the Mediterranean Greece. The $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ enrichment of this study is higher than information from the Bavarian bentonites ([Köster and Gilg, 2015](#)) as well as than the Early Holocene ground water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of the Munich ([Rauert et al., 1993](#)). This observation is

plausible if the time scale of the present study had the warmest and driest spell in comparison to the others. Moreover the observation is not in congruence with that of the humid Siwalik Himalaya, Pakistan (-10.18‰) during 11.1-12.2 Ma ([Behrensmeyer et al., 2007](#); [Quade and Cerling, 1995](#)). Hence the enrichment of the studied temporal profile seems to be driven by a combination of factors.

Figure 38: Regional spatiotemporal d¹⁸O status in comparison with this study.

V.D. Relevance of the Irsee and HAM isotopic signature in light of the Mid to Late Miocene paleoenvironment:

The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ enrichment profile from 12.207 – 11.154 Ma represents floral components that were adaptive to the ongoing intensified water stress. On the other hand despite having different temporal means, the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values have similar trend irrespective of the age clusters where the most depleted values are at the bottom and the enriched ones are at the top. This obliquity is apparently suggestive of intensifying humidity and/or coldness towards the respective younger stratum. However absence of steady stepwise shift either in the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ or

the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ profile insinuates that the region had few smaller climate cycles during the Middle to Late Miocene shift when juxtaposed with the precedent or the following time.

Although re-depletion of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in the youngest span is challenging the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ based assumption but as the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ mean difference of the ELM and LMM is not significant hence the apparent re-depletion was not supposed to hinder the development of the aridity tolerant flora towards the younger age. Whereas from the synchronous $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ it can be apparently considered that the depleted $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ trend otherwise denotes a gradual cooler and/or drier environment ([Pound et al., 2012](#)) in this part of the Paratethys realm perhaps under influence of the Mi events ([Kocsis et al., 2008](#); [Miller et al., 2005](#); [Miller et al., 1991](#); [Westerhold et al., 2005](#)).

Figure 39: The $d^{13}\text{C}$ and $d^{18}\text{O}$ profiles from the Mid to Late Miocene transition in the Irsee and HAM.

Hereafter the depleted $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ mean of the ~0.2 Myr wide oldest age cluster (MMM), particularly in its earlier span can be indicative of Mi4 cooling effect ([Cooke et al., 2008](#); [Lourens and Hilgen, 1997](#)). Delineation of a C3 dominant paleovegetation between 12.207 Ma and 12.013 Ma is coherent with the humid environment signature from the synchronous depleted $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ profile. Globally an elevated $p\text{CO}_2$ and relatively high MAP of this span than the following sections ([Cooke et al., 2008](#); [Cramer et al., 2009](#); [Miller et al., 1991](#); [Mosbrugger et al., 2005](#); [Pagani et al., 1999](#); [Pagani et al., 2005](#); [Tzanova et al., 2015](#)) are in support of this assumption. The initial enrichment in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ could be from some lineages of subtropical dry deciduous C3 flora of the precedent lower Miocene era ([Böhme et al., 2007](#); [Jiménez-Moreno and Suc, 2007](#)) which could regain their profusion for a while under a cool and arid climate because of the Mi4 ([Cooke et al., 2008](#); [Lourens and Hilgen, 1997](#)) as the excavated faunal fossils ([Kirscher et al., 2016](#)) do not satisfy presence of desert adapted C3 taxa in this region.

In the following ~0.1 Myr time period (LMM) the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ enrichment was remain within the Middle Miocene C3 domain but the share of C3 components in the paleovegetation had been reduced by ~4%. Although the progressions of the drier biomes (temperate deciduous savanna biome) that may contain the C4 taxa progressed at the end of Seravallian ([Ivanov and Böhme, 2011](#); [Pound et al., 2012](#)) because of lowered $p\text{CO}_2$ and reduction in precipitation seasonality ([Holbourn et al., 2018](#)) but extreme cold could nullify the C4 expansion ([Sage, 2004](#)). Thus the synchronous Mi5 ([Cooke et al., 2008](#); [Miller et al., 1991](#); [Turco et al., 2001](#); [Westerhold et al., 2005](#)) could prevent the C4 expansion in this spatial range. Moreover the parallel paleozoological evidences ([Böhme et al., 2011](#)) besides the paleobotanical views about extensive thermophylous C3 flora in subtropical Western Paratethys realm ([Barrón et al., 2010](#); [Cojan et al., 2013](#); [Ivanov et al., 2011](#); [Jiménez-Moreno and Suc, 2007](#); [Mosbrugger et al., 2005](#)) is not in favour of C4 profusion in this profile during the Middle Miocene. Although the $p\text{CO}_2$ observation is still disputed ([Zhang et al., 2013](#)) [Fig.40] but as higher $p\text{CO}_2$ is not a constraint for the C4 vegetation development ([Sage, 2004](#)) so occurrence of the C4 taxa even under a elevate $p\text{CO}_2$ level near the verge of the Late Miocene is not impossible.

Figure 40: Comparison of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values of this study with concomitant global climatic conditions.

Accordingly the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ interpretation for C3 dominant taxa in the Irsee and HAM till the 11.598 Ma is straightforward until the synchronous enrichment of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in comparison to

the entire temporal range is ignored. With a subtropical nature the study area was supposed to be warmer and drier at the beginning of the Tortonian or early Late Miocene (~11.6 Ma) than today ([Böhme et al., 2008](#); [Mosbrugger et al., 2005](#)). Thus the heaviest $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ at 11.661 Ma could be reflective of prevalent warm and dry spell in the Paratethys realm ([Böhme, 2004](#); [Böhme et al., 2008](#); [Böhme et al., 2011](#); [Mosbrugger et al., 2005](#)). In addition, reduction of canopy effect as implied from the declined $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ could result in an evaporised enrichment of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in the local soil ([Behrensmeyer et al., 2007](#); [Bocherens and Drucker, 2013](#)). Although the waning of 0.51‰ $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ from the preceding age could be a good factor of 0.64‰ $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ enrichment ([Behrensmeyer et al., 2007](#)) but not a primary one in this present study because of the Late Miocene C3 vegetation spectrum ([Tippie and Pagani, 2007](#)).

Being situated in the south-central Europe, the moistures from the North Sea and the Paratethys had enriched the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of the region during the Middle Miocene ([Böhme, 2004](#)). However severe evaporative enrichment of the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ driven by the tectonically reorganized hypersaline Paratethys ([Harzhauser et al., 2007](#); [Latal et al., 2004](#); [Rostovtseva and Kuleshov, 2016](#)) could produce heavier $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PC}}$ from the 11.685 Ma towards the upper chronologies as substantiated by the most positive $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ reading of this study at 11.661 Ma. The heaviest $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ reading are also in harmony with the then global oceanic trend ([Harzhauser et al., 2007](#); [Piller and Harzhauser, 2005](#); [Zachos et al., 2001](#)) besides the contemporaneous warmer Atlantic inflow to the Mediterranean ([Hardenbol et al., 1998](#); [Kocsis et al., 2008](#); [Lear et al., 2003](#)). Therefore the consecutive evaporative enrichment seemed to have stronger influence over the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ than the Mi5 event in this spatiotemporal range of the then Paratethys realm. And under such an environment comprising of depleted $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ likewise of this study is not unparallel ([Behrensmeyer et al., 2007](#); [Quade and Cerling, 1995](#); [Rostovtseva and Kuleshov, 2016](#)). Moreover as the hypersalinity can support C4 propagation under low $p\text{CO}_2$ ([Sage, 2004](#)) so the C4 signature from a relatively more enriched $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ alongside the synchronous $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ pattern in the LMM profile than the foregoing profile cannot be ruled out at ~11.6 Ma when the Paratethys was only marginally marine ([Kocsis et al., 2008](#); [Latal et al., 2004](#)). However as the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ of the LMM and the MMM was not significantly different hence paleovegetation of the LMM group can be put within the vicinity of the Late Miocene C3 realm ([Cojan et al., 2013](#)).

The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ enrichment pattern from the 11.354 to 11.154 Ma (ELM) reflects further diminishing of pure C3 taxa in the paleovegetation. By the Mid Miocene (15.3 Ma) C4 grasses had advanced to high latitudes of Europe ([Cojan et al., 2013](#); [Holbourn et al., 2018](#); [Latorre et al., 1997](#); [Quade and Cerling, 1995](#)); hence the enriched $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value of the ELM is signifying existence of C4 taxa that is in congruence with the Late Miocene C3 & C4 mixed vegetation domain ([Cojan et al., 2013](#)) possibly in a warm temperate paleoecosystem ([Pound et al., 2012](#)). The observation is analogous with intensifying aridity in the Paratethys realm ([Böhme, 2004](#); [Böhme et al., 2008](#); [Böhme et al., 2011](#); [Rostovtseva and Kuleshov, 2016](#)) although the timing of beginning of the drier climate is disputed ([Utescher et al., 2011](#)). This temperature assumption is also favoured by the parallel global oceanic temperature ([Zachos et al., 2001](#)) [Fig.36] but not by the concomitant Mediterranean temperature ([Tzanova et al., 2015](#)) and the North hemisphere temperature ([De Boer et al., 2010](#)). Furthermore the global sea level fall ([De Boer et al., 2010](#)) could lessen the effect of the warm Atlantic Bottom Water current on the Mediterranean [Fig.41].

As the Mi5 was active also in the initial periods of the Late Miocene ([Cooke et al., 2008](#); [Miller et al., 1991](#); [Turco et al., 2001](#); [Westerhold et al., 2005](#)) so the most depleted $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ at 11.222 Ma could be the aftermath of the nearest Mi5 crest ([Turco et al., 2001](#)) when the inflated water stress perhaps promoted the C4 profusion besides aridity tolerant C3 plants which the synchronous lightest $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ is signaling. If a minimum of 20% biomass presence is considered as significant contributor to any paleoecosystem ([Edwards et al., 2010](#)) then despite having the apparent signature except the 11.222 Ma, the C4 taxa had no substantial role in the paleoecosystem of Irsee and Hammerschmiede. Henceforth it can be assumed that the ELM had a definitely C3 and C4 mixed vegetation with a dominance of the C3 taxa until 11.232 Ma. On the other hand the concurrent $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ profile statistics is not suggestive of a significantly different paleoenvironment in comparison to the forgoing era [Fig. 25, 26, 27 of Result section]. Hence it could be possible that either the reduction of canopy effect in the paleovegetation and/or the intensified marginality of the Paratethys Sea had maintained an enriched $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ profile in Irsee and HAM region even in a cooler environment

(Behrensmeyer et al., 2007; Bocherens and Drucker, 2013; Harzhauser et al., 2007; Latal et al., 2004; Rostovtseva and Kuleshov, 2016).

Figure 41: Comparison of d18O values of this study with concomitant global climatic conditions.

The enrichment of the youngest $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ profile is in fact congruous with the concomitant alkalinity regime of the Paratethys Sea ([Harzhauser et al., 2007](#)). Furthermore it could be possible that the rising temperature of the eastern Atlantic current from 11.5 Ma to 10 Ma overcome the synchronous Global cooling effect ([De Boer et al., 2010](#); [Kocsis et al., 2008](#); [Lear et al., 2003](#)) and brought warm moistures to this part of the Paratethys realm, likewise of contemporary tropical regions. In that case escalated rain could not result in depletion of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values in the ELM profile because of the *amount effect* ([Dansgaard, 1964](#); [Sharp, 2007](#)); but the water stress signature from the synchronous $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values is against the inference of a humid climate for the ELM profile. Nevertheless even in an arid climate the strengthened Atlantic inflow could lead depletion in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values because of its intent attribute ([Stumpp et al., 2014](#)).

The synchronization between the global oceanic $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ ([Zachos et al., 2001](#)) and the $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PC}}$ of this study [Fig.36] fortifies the suggestion of a warmer dry spell during the early Late Miocene. In the past, depleted $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ signature during the summer monsoon is apparent during the last interglacial in Northern Asia ([Yang et al., 2012](#)). Moreover the evaporative $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ enrichment during the dry season precipitation in the modern Mediterranean region is also common ([Cojan et al., 2013](#); [Otieno et al., 2006](#)). Henceforth with a subtropical climate ([Böhme et al., 2007](#); [Harzhauser et al., 2007](#); [Piller and Harzhauser, 2005](#)) and harbinger of a “wash house” Europe (10.2-9.8 Ma) ([Böhme et al., 2008](#)) the *amount effect* was supposed to be present also in the relatively drier transition phase of question. Henceforth the statistically insignificant $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values of the younger profiles of this study could be reflective of *amount effect* like conditions in a water stress environment which the synchronous enriched $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values suggest. Insignificant correlation between carbon and oxygen isotopic enrichment by photosynthesis and evaporation is apparent where several secondary complex processes are interacting ([Léveillé et al., 2007](#); [Volk et al., 2011](#)). And therefore it can be assumed that at least few interacting factors had impacts over the paleoenvironment in Irsee and Hammerschmiede during the switchover from the Mid to the Late Miocene. The concomitant geoclimatic events that possibly had influence on the concerned paleoenvironmental shift are delineated in the following illustration [Fig.42].

Figure 42: Global and regional geoclimatic events concomitant with this study and the changing paleoenvironment model of the Irsee and HAM. The black arrows indicate the direction of increasing magnitude of the respective event. [Courtesy: Clipart Library]

Reference:

- Antarctic Ice Sheet: K.G. Miller et al, 1991; P. J. Cooke et al, 2008.
- North Hemisphere Ice Sheet: T. Fronval & E. Jansen, 1996; T. Westerhold et al, 2005.
- Global Sea Level: D. Be Boer et al, 2010.
- Mi5***: K.G. Miller et al. 1991; T. Westerhold et al, 2005.
- Mi5**: P. J. Cooke et al, 2008.
- Mi5*: E. Turco et al., 2001.
- Mi4*: L. J. Lourens & F. J. Hilgen, 1997.
- CM7: P. J. Cooke et al, 2008; Y.V. Rostovtseva & V. N. Kuleshov, 2016.
- Warm Atlantic Inflow: C. H. Lear e al, 2003; L. Kocsis et al, 2007.
- Alpine Orogenesis: L. Kocsis et al 2007.
- Mediterranean temperature: A. Tzanova et al, 2015.
- Marginal Paratethys Enrichment: M. Harzhauser et al, 2007; Christine Latal et al, 2004; Y. V. Rostovtseva & V. N. Kuleshov, 2016.
- Water stress & Evaporative enrichment by canopy effect: (Isotopic interpretation from this study).

VI. CONCLUSION

Interactions of the temperature, evaporation, moisture type and source in addition to the tectonic reorganization of the Paratehys have made the reconstruction of intermediate environment between the Middle to the Late Miocene of Irsee and Hammerschmiede from the pedogenic carbonate intricate. But the multifaceted outcomes of this study are not completely unparallel when compared with the synchronous paleoecosystem and paleoclimatic events that have been established yet.

The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ profile signature implies retreating of the C3 vegetation towards the younger temporal units possibly for increasing water stress in the paleoecosystem. Synchronous $p\text{CO}_2$, global cooling and short global warming could lead the appearance of C4 taxa by the Late Middle Miocene which was later expanded under a subtropical environment around the Early Late Miocene. The heaviest $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ is suggestive of C4 components at 11.222 Ma rather than being an outlier because of favourable environment. Thus the declining canopy effect on the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values of this paleoecosystem cannot be ruled out.

The $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ profile has marks of global cooling events Mi4 and Mi5 with the former at the base of the Mid Middle Miocene and the latter from ~11.6 Ma onwards to the beginning of the Tortonian. However the hypersaline Parathetys and the warmer Atlantic Ocean inflow seemed to have deeper effects than the Mi events on the regional climate that led the fluctuation of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ profile. In addition the dry tropic like settings could also result in *amount effect* at the younger profiles.

Because of the contrast in the precipitations, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{PC}}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{PC}}$ have weak correlation in this study. The $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ variability implies that the paleoclimate of Irsee and HAM during the Mid to Late Miocene was controlled by a combination of geoclimatic events. The composed isotopic values indicate relatively a drier and warmer paleoecosystem in this region from the Late Middle Miocene than the modern time but it was not vapid. Despite having water stress, the Irsee and Hammerschmiede had not become xeric rather was mesic which is in agreement with the concerned fossil evidences. This study postulates that Mi

events were instrumental for the arrival of the C4 taxa at these sites which afterwards proliferated under the favourable influence of the marginal Paratethys Sea and the warm Atlantic Ocean current.

REFERENCES

1. Abreu, V.S. and Anderson, J.B. (1998) Glacial eustasy during the Cenozoic: sequence stratigraphic implications. *AAPG bulletin* 82, 1385-1400.
2. Achyuthan, H. (2003) Petrologic analysis and geochemistry of the Late Neogene-Early Quaternary hardpan calcretes of Western Rajasthan, India. *Quaternary International* 106, 3-10.
3. Achyuthan, H., Quade, J., Roe, L. and Placzek, C. (2007) Stable isotopic composition of pedogenic carbonates from the eastern margin of the Thar Desert, Rajasthan, India. *Quaternary International* 162-163, 50-60.
4. Amundson, R.G., Chadwick, O.A., Sowers, J.M. and Doner, H.E. (1988) Relationship between climate and vegetation and the stable carbon isotope chemistry of soils in the eastern Mojave Desert, Nevada. *Quaternary Research* 29, 245-254.
5. Araguás-Araguás, L., Froehlich, K. and Rozanski, K. (2000) Deuterium and oxygen-18 isotope composition of precipitation and atmospheric moisture. *Hydrological processes* 14, 1341-1355.
6. Arakaki, M., Christin, P.-A., Nyffeler, R., Lendel, A., Eggli, U., Ogburn, R.M., Spriggs, E., Moore, M.J. and Edwards, E.J. (2011) Contemporaneous and recent radiations of the world's major succulent plant lineages. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 108, 8379-8384.
7. Barrón, E., Rivas-Carballo, R., Postigo-Mijarra, J.M., Alcalde-Olivares, C., Vieira, M., Castro, L., Pais, J. and Valle-Hernández, M. (2010) The Cenozoic vegetation of the Iberian Peninsula: a synthesis. *Review of palaeobotany and palynology* 162, 382-402.
8. Behrensmeyer, A.K., Quade, J., Cerling, T.E., Kappelman, J., Khan, I.A., Copeland, P., Roe, L., Hicks, J., Stubblefield, P. and Willis, B.J. (2007) The structure and rate of late Miocene expansion of C4 plants: Evidence from lateral variation in stable isotopes in paleosols of the Siwalik Group, northern Pakistan. *Geological Society of America Bulletin* 119, 1486-1505.
9. Bernor, R.L., Kovar-Eder, J., Lipscomb, D., Rögl, F., Sen, S. and Tobien, H. (1988) Systematic, stratigraphic, and paleoenvironmental contexts of first-appearing Hipparion in the Vienna Basin, Austria. *Journal of Vertebrate Paleontology* 8, 427-452.
10. Bocherens, H. and Drucker, D.G. (2013) Terrestrial Teeth and Bones, in: Elias, S.A. (Ed.), *The Encyclopedia of Quaternary Science*, 2nd ed. Elsevier, Amsterdam, pp. 304-314.

- 11.** Böhme, M. (2003) The Miocene climatic optimum: evidence from ectothermic vertebrates of Central Europe. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 195, 389-401.
- 12.** Böhme, M. (2004) Migration history of air-breathing fishes reveals Neogene atmospheric circulation patterns. *Geology* 32, 393-396.
- 13.** Böhme, M. (2017) Field Lectures, Hammerschmiede (Terrestrische Ökosysteme - Grabungs- und Laborpraktikum - 2017).
- 14.** Böhme, M. (2018) Field Lectures, Hammerschmiede (Terrestrische Ökosysteme - Grabungs- und Laborpraktikum - 2018).
- 15.** Böhme, M., Bruch, A.A. and Selmeier, A. (2007) The reconstruction of Early and Middle Miocene climate and vegetation in Southern Germany as determined from the fossil wood flora. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 253, 91-114.
- 16.** Böhme, M., Gregor, H.-J. and Heissig, K. (2002) The Ries and Steinheim meteorite impacts and their effect on environmental conditions in time and space, in: Buffetaut, E., Koeberl, C. (Eds.), *Geological and biological effects of impact events*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp. 217-235.
- 17.** Böhme, M., Ilg, A. and Winklhofer, M. (2008) Late Miocene “washhouse” climate in Europe. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 275, 393-401.
- 18.** Böhme, M., Spassov, N., Ebner, M., Geraads, D., Hristova, L., Kirscher, U., Kötter, S., Linnemann, U., Prieto, J. and Roussiakis, S. (2017) Messinian age and savannah environment of the possible hominin *Graecopithecus* from Europe. *PloS one* 12, 1-31.
- 19.** Böhme, M., Winklhofer, M. and Ilg, A. (2011) Miocene precipitation in Europe: temporal trends and spatial gradients. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 304, 212-218.
- 20.** Bruch, A., Utescher, T., Mosbrugger, V., Gabrielyan, I. and Ivanov, D. (2006) Late Miocene climate in the circum-Alpine realm—a quantitative analysis of terrestrial palaeofloras. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 238, 270-280.

- 21.** Bruch, A.A., Utescher, T. and Mosbrugger, V. (2011) Precipitation patterns in the Miocene of Central Europe and the development of continentality. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 304, 202-211.
- 22.** Campani, M., Mulch, A., Kempf, O., Schlunegger, F. and Mancktelow, N. (2012) Miocene paleotopography of the Central Alps. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 337, 174-185.
- 23.** Catoni, M., Falsone, G. and Bonifacio, E. (2012) Assessing the origin of carbonates in a complex soil with a suite of analytical methods. *Geoderma* 175, 47-57.
- 24.** Cerling, T.E. (1984) The stable isotopic composition of modern soil carbonate and its relationship to climate. *Earth and Planetary science letters* 71, 229-240.
- 25.** Cerling, T.E., Harris, J.M., MacFadden, B.J., Leakey, M.G., Quade, J., Eisenmann, V. and Ehleringer, J.R. (1997) Global vegetation change through the Miocene/Pliocene boundary. *Nature* 389, 153 -158.
- 26.** Cerling, T.E. and Quade, J. (1993) Stable Carbon and Oxygen Isotopes in Soil Carbonates. *Climate Change in Continental Isotopic Records. Geophysical Monograph. American Geophysical Union* 78, 217-231.
- 27.** Cerling, T.E., Quade, J., Wang, Y. and Bowman, J. (1989) Carbon isotopes in soils and palaeosols as ecology and palaeoecology indicators. *Nature* 341, 138.
- 28.** Cerling, T.E., Solomon, D.K., Quade, J. and Bowman, J.R. (1991) On the isotopic composition of carbon in soil carbon dioxide. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 55, 3403-3405.
- 29.** Chamberlain, C.P. and Poage, M.A. (2000) Reconstructing the paleotopography of mountain belts from the isotopic composition of authigenic minerals. *Geology* 28, 115-118.
- 30.** Choi, Y., Wang, Y., Hsieh, Y.P. and Robinson, L. (2001) Vegetation succession and carbon sequestration in a coastal wetland in northwest Florida: Evidence from carbon isotopes. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles* 15, 311-319.
- 31.** Christin, P.-A., Besnard, G., Samaritani, E., Duvall, M.R., Hodkinson, T.R., Savolainen, V. and Salamin, N. (2008) Oligocene CO₂ decline promoted C₄ photosynthesis in grasses. *Current Biology* 18, 37-43.

- 32.** Cojan, I., Bialkowski, A., Gillot, T. and Renard, M. (2013) Paleoenvironnement and paleoclimate reconstruction for the early to middle Miocene from stable isotopes in pedogenic carbonates (Digne-Valensole basin, southeastern France). *Bulletin de la Société Géologique de France* 184, 583-599.
- 33.** Cooke, P.J., Nelson, C.S. and Crundwell, M.P. (2008) Miocene isotope zones, paleotemperatures, and carbon maxima events at intermediate water-depth, Site 593, Southwest Pacific. *New Zealand Journal of Geology and Geophysics* 51, 1-22.
- 34.** Cramer, B., Toggweiler, J., Wright, J., Katz, M. and Miller, K. (2009) Ocean overturning since the Late Cretaceous: Inferences from a new benthic foraminiferal isotope compilation. *Paleoceanography* 24.
- 35.** Criss, R.E. (1999) Principles of stable isotope distribution. Oxford University Press Inc., New York.
- 36.** Dansgaard, W. (1964) Stable isotopes in precipitation. *Tellus* 16, 436-468.
- 37.** De Boer, B., Van de Wal, R., Bintanja, R., Lourens, L. and Tuenter, E. (2010) Cenozoic global ice-volume and temperature simulations with 1-D ice-sheet models forced by benthic $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ records. *Annals of Glaciology* 51, 23-33.
- 38.** Doppler, G. (1989) Zur Stratigraphie der nördlichen Vorlandmolasse in Bayerisch-Schwaben. *Geologica Bavarica* 94, 83-133.
- 39.** Dworkin, S., Nordt, L. and Atchley, S. (2005) Determining terrestrial paleotemperatures using the oxygen isotopic composition of pedogenic carbonate. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 237, 56-68.
- 40.** Edwards, E.J., Osborne, C.P., Strömberg, C.A., Smith, S.A. and Consortium, C.G. (2010) The origins of C4 grasslands: integrating evolutionary and ecosystem science. *science* 328, 587-591.
- 41.** Ehleringer, J.R., Cerling, T.E. and Helliker, B.R. (1997) C4 photosynthesis, atmospheric CO₂, and climate. *Oecologia* 112, 285-299.
- 42.** Ehleringer, J.R., Sage, R.F., Flanagan, L.B. and Pearcy, R.W. (1991) Climate change and the evolution of C4 photosynthesis. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 6, 95-99.

- 43.** Eronen, J.T. and Rössner, G.E. (2007) Wetland paradise lost: Miocene community dynamics in large herbivorous mammals from the German Molasse Basin. *Evolutionary Ecology Research* 9, 471-494.
- 44.** Eswaran, H., Reich, P., Kimble, J., Beinroth, F., Padmanabhan, E. and Moncharoen, P. (2000) Global carbon stocks, in: Lal, R., Kimble, J.M., Eswaran, H., Stewart, B.A. (Eds.), *Global climate change and pedogenic carbonates*. Lewis Publ., Boca Raton, FL., pp. 15–26.
- 45.** Farquhar, G.D., Ehleringer, J.R. and Hubick, K.T. (1989) Carbon isotope discrimination and photosynthesis. *Annual review of plant biology* 40, 503-537.
- 46.** Fortelius, M., Eronen, J., Liu, L., Pushkina, D., Tesakov, A., Vislobokova, I. and Zhang, Z. (2006) Late Miocene and Pliocene large land mammals and climatic changes in Eurasia. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 238, 219-227.
- 47.** Fox, D.L., Honey, J.G., Martin, R.A. and Peláez-Campomanes, P. (2012) Pedogenic carbonate stable isotope record of environmental change during the Neogene in the southern Great Plains, southwest Kansas, USA: carbon isotopes and the evolution of C4-dominated grasslands. *Geological Society of America Bulletin* 124, 444-462.
- 48.** Friedman, I. and O'Neil, J.R. (1977) *Data of geochemistry: Compilation of stable isotope fractionation factors of geochemical interest*. US Government Printing Office.
- 49.** Fronval, T. and Jansen, E. (1993) Late Neogene paleoclimates and paleoceanography in the Iceland-Norwegian Sea: evidence from the Iceland and Voering Plateaus, in: Thiede, J., Myhre, A.M., F., J.V., J.G.L., Ruddiman, W.F. (Eds.), *PROCEEDINGS-OCEAN DRILLING PROGRAM SCIENTIFIC RESULTS*. NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION, pp. 455-468.
- 50.** Fry, B. (2008) *Stable isotope ecology*. Springer, USA.
- 51.** Fuss, J., Prieto, J. and Böhme, M. (2015) Revision of the boselaphin bovid *Miotragocerus monacensis* Stromer, 1928 (Mammalia, Bovidae) at the Middle to Late Miocene transition in Central Europe. *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie-Abhandlungen* 276, 229-265.
- 52.** Garzzone, C.N., Hoke, G.D., Libarkin, J.C., Withers, S., MacFadden, B., Eiler, J., Ghosh, P. and Mulch, A. (2008) Rise of the Andes. *Science* 320, 1304-1307.

- 53.** Ghosh, P., Adkins, J., Affek, H., Balta, B., Guo, W., Schauble, E.A., Schrag, D. and Eiler, J.M. (2006a) ^{13}C – ^{18}O bonds in carbonate minerals: a new kind of paleothermometer. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 70, 1439-1456.
- 54.** Ghosh, P., Bhattacharya, S. and Jani, R. (1995) Palaeoclimate and palaeovegetation in central India during the Upper Cretaceous based on stable isotope composition of the palaeosol carbonates. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 114, 285-296.
- 55.** Ghosh, P., Garzzone, C.N. and Eiler, J.M. (2006b) Rapid uplift of the Altiplano revealed through ^{13}C - ^{18}O bonds in paleosol carbonates. *Science* 311, 511-515.
- 56.** Goldner, A., Herold, N. and Huber, M. (2014) The Challenge of Simulating the Warmth of the Mid-Miocene Climatic Optimum in CESM1. *Climate of the Past*.
- 57.** Han, J., Keppens, E., Liu, T., Paepe, R. and Jiang, W. (1997) Stable isotope composition of the carbonate concretion in loess and climate change. *Quaternary International* 37, 37-43.
- 58.** Hardenbol, J., Thierry, J., Farley, M.B., Jacquin, T., De Graciansky, P.-C. and Vail, P.R. (1998) Mesozoic and Cenozoic sequence chronostratigraphic framework of European basins. SEPM Society for Sedimentary Geology, Special Publication 60, 3-13.
- 59.** Harzhauser, M., Latal, C. and Piller, W.E. (2007) The stable isotope archive of Lake Pannon as a mirror of Late Miocene climate change. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 249, 335-350.
- 60.** Hattersley, P. (1983) The distribution of C_3 and C_4 grasses in Australia in relation to climate. *Oecologia* 57, 113-128.
- 61.** Herbert, T.D., Lawrence, K.T., Tzanova, A., Peterson, L.C., Caballero-Gill, R. and Kelly, C.S. (2016) Late Miocene global cooling and the rise of modern ecosystems. *Nature Geoscience* 9, 843.
- 62.** Hoefs, J. (2004) *Stable isotope geochemistry*, 5th rev. and updated ed. Springer-Verlag, Berlin.
- 63.** Holbourn, A.E., Kuhnt, W., Clemens, S., Prell, W. and Andersen, N. (2013) Middle to late Miocene stepwise climate cooling: Evidence from a high-resolution deep water isotope curve spanning 8 million years. *Paleoceanography* 28, 688-699.

- 64.** Holbourn, A.E., Kuhnt, W., Clemens, S.C., Kochhann, K.G., Jöhnck, J., Lübbers, J. and Andersen, N. (2018) Late Miocene climate cooling and intensification of southeast Asian winter monsoon. *Nature communications* 9, 1-13.
- 65.** Homewood, P., Allen, P. and Williams, G. (1986) Dynamics of the Molasse Basin of western Switzerland, in: Allen, P.A., Homewood, P. (Eds.), *Foreland basins. Spec Publ The International Association of Sedimentologists*, Blackwell, Oxford, pp. 199-217.
- 66.** Horton, T.W., Defliese, W.F., Tripathi, A.K. and Oze, C. (2016) Evaporation induced ^{18}O and ^{13}C enrichment in lake systems: a global perspective on hydrologic balance effects. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 131, 365-379.
- 67.** Hsieh, J.C., Chadwick, O.A., Kelly, E.F. and Savin, S.M. (1998a) Oxygen isotopic composition of soil water: quantifying evaporation and transpiration. *Geoderma* 82, 269-293.
- 68.** Hsieh, J.C., Savin, S.M., Kelly, E.F. and Chadwick, O.A. (1998b) Measurement of soil-water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values by direct equilibration with CO_2 . *Geoderma* 82, 255-268.
- 69.** Hüsing, S., Hilgen, F., Aziz, H.A. and Krijgsman, W. (2007) Completing the Neogene geological time scale between 8.5 and 12.5 Ma. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 253, 340-358.
- 70.** Ivanov, D., Utescher, T., Mosbrugger, V., Syabryaj, S., Djordjević-Milutinović, D. and Molchanoff, S. (2011) Miocene vegetation and climate dynamics in Eastern and Central Paratethys (Southeastern Europe). *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 304, 262-275.
- 71.** Ivanov, M. and Böhme, M. (2011) Snakes from Griesbeckerzell (Langhian, Early Badenian), North Alpine Foreland Basin (Germany), with comments on the evolution of snake faunas in Central Europe during the Miocene climatic optimum. *Geodiversitas* 33, 411-450.
- 72.** Jiménez-Moreno, G. and Suc, J.-P. (2007) Middle Miocene latitudinal climatic gradient in Western Europe: evidence from pollen records. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 253, 208-225.
- 73.** Kirscher, U., Prieto, J., Bachtadse, V., Aziz, H.A., Doppler, G., Hagmaier, M. and Böhme, M. (2016) A biochronologic tie-point for the base of the Tortonian stage in European terrestrial settings: Magnetostratigraphy of the topmost Upper Freshwater Molasse

sediments of the North Alpine Foreland Basin in Bavaria (Germany). *Newsletters on Stratigraphy* 49, 445-467.

74. Koch, P.L. (1998) Isotopic reconstruction of past continental environments. *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences* 26, 573-613.

75. Kocsis, L., Vennemann, T., Fontignie, D., Baumgartner, C., Montanari, A. and Jelen, B. (2008) Oceanographic and climatic evolution of the Miocene Mediterranean deduced from Nd, Sr, C, and O isotope compositions of marine fossils and sediments. *Paleoceanography and Paleoclimatology* 23, 1-20.

76. Köster, M. and Gilg, H. (2015) Pedogenic, palustrine and groundwater dolomite formation in non-marine bentonites (Bavaria, Germany). *Clay Minerals* 50, 163-184.

77. Kürschner, W.M., Kvaček, Z. and Dilcher, D.L. (2008) The impact of Miocene atmospheric carbon dioxide fluctuations on climate and the evolution of terrestrial ecosystems. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 105, 449-453.

78. Lachniet, M.S. (2009) Climatic and environmental controls on speleothem oxygen-isotope values. *Quaternary Science Reviews* 28, 412-432.

79. Lal, R. (2008) Sequestration of atmospheric CO₂ in global carbon pools. *Energy & Environmental Science* 1, 86-100.

80. Latal, C., Piller, W.E. and Harzhauser, M. (2004) Palaeoenvironmental reconstructions by stable isotopes of Middle Miocene gastropods of the Central Paratethys. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 211, 157-169.

81. Latorre, C., Quade, J. and McIntosh, W.C. (1997) The expansion of C₄ grasses and global change in the late Miocene: stable isotope evidence from the Americas. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 146, 83-96.

82. Lear, C.H., Rosenthal, Y. and Wright, J.D. (2003) The closing of a seaway: ocean water masses and global climate change. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 210, 425-436.

83. Lee, Y.I. and Hisada, K.-i. (1999) Stable isotopic composition of pedogenic carbonates of the Early Cretaceous Shimonoseki Subgroup, western Honshu, Japan. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 153, 127-138.

- 84.** Leone, G., Bonadonna, F. and Zanchetta, G. (2000) Stable isotope record in mollusca and pedogenic carbonate from Late Pliocene soils of Central Italy. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 163, 115-131.
- 85.** Lveill, R., Longstaffe, F. and Fyfe, W. (2007) An isotopic and geochemical study of carbonate-clay mineralization in basaltic caves: abiotic versus microbial processes. *Geobiology* 5, 235-249.
- 86.** Lohmann, K.C. (1988) Geochemical patterns of meteoric diagenetic systems and their application to studies of paleokarst, in: JAMES, N.P., CHOQUETTE, P.W. (Eds.), *Paleokarst*. Springer-Verlag, New York, pp. 58-80.
- 87.** Lourens, L. and Hilgen, F. (1997) Long-periodic variations in the Earth's obliquity and their relation to third-order eustatic cycles and late Neogene glaciations. *Quaternary International* 40, 43-52.
- 88.** McCrea, J.M. (1950) On the isotopic chemistry of carbonates and a paleotemperature scale. *Journal of Chemical Physics* 18, 849-857.
- 89.** Menndez, I., Cano, A.R.G., Yelo, B.A.G., Domingo, L., Domingo, M.S., Cantalapiedra, J.L., Blanco, F. and Fernndez, M.H. (2017) Body-size structure of Central Iberian mammal fauna reveals semidesertic conditions during the middle Miocene Global Cooling Event. *PloS One* 12, 1-32.
- 90.** Miller, K.G., Kominz, M.A., Browning, J.V., Wright, J.D., Mountain, G.S., Katz, M.E., Sugarman, P.J., Cramer, B.S., Christie-Blick, N. and Pekar, S.F. (2005) The Phanerozoic record of global sea-level change. *science* 310, 1293-1298.
- 91.** Miller, K.G., Wright, J.D. and Fairbanks, R.G. (1991) Unlocking the ice house: Oligocene-Miocene oxygen isotopes, eustasy, and margin erosion. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Solid Earth* 96, 6829-6848.
- 92.** Mosbrugger, V., Utescher, T. and Dilcher, D.L. (2005) Cenozoic continental climatic evolution of Central Europe. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 102, 14964-14969.
- 93.** Moy-Sol, S., Alba, D.M., Almcija, S., Casanovas-Vilar, I., Khler, M., De Esteban-Trivigno, S., Robles, J.M., Galindo, J. and Fortuny, J. (2009) A unique Middle Miocene European hominoid and the origins of the great ape and human clade. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 106, 9601-9606.

- 94.** Nakatsukasa, M. (2004) Acquisition of bipedalism: the Miocene hominoid record and modern analogues for bipedal protohominids. *Journal of Anatomy* 204, 385-402.
- 95.** Newton, J. (2010) Stable isotope ecology. *Encyclopedia of Life Sciences (ELS)*, 1-7.
- 96.** O'Leary, M.H. (1981) Carbon isotope fractionation in plants. *Phytochemistry* 20, 553-567.
- 97.** O'Leary, M.H. (1988) Carbon isotopes in photosynthesis. *Bioscience* 38, 328-336.
- 98.** O'Neil, J.R., Clayton, R.N. and Mayeda, T.K. (1969) Oxygen isotope fractionation in divalent metal carbonates. *The Journal of Chemical Physics* 51, 5547-5558.
- 99.** Otieno, D., Kurz-Besson, C., Liu, J., Schmidt, M., David, T., Siegwolf, R., Pereira, J. and Tenhunen, J. (2006) Seasonal variations in soil and plant water status in a *Quercus suber* L. stand: roots as determinants of tree productivity and survival in the Mediterranean-type ecosystem. *Plant and Soil* 283, 119-135.
- 100.** Pagani, M., Arthur, M.A. and Freeman, K.H. (1999) Miocene evolution of atmospheric carbon dioxide. *Paleoceanography* 14, 273-292.
- 101.** Pagani, M., Zachos, J.C., Freeman, K.H., Tipple, B. and Bohaty, S. (2005) Marked decline in atmospheric carbon dioxide concentrations during the Paleogene. *Science* 309, 600-603.
- 102.** Passey, B.H., Ayliffe, L.K., Kaakinen, A., Zhang, Z., Eronen, J.T., Zhu, Y., Zhou, L., Cerling, T.E. and Fortelius, M. (2009) Strengthened East Asian summer monsoons during a period of high-latitude warmth? Isotopic evidence from Mio-Pliocene fossil mammals and soil carbonates from northern China. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 277, 443-452.
- 103.** Passey, B.H., Cerling, T.E., Perkins, M.E., Voorhies, M.R., Harris, J.M. and Tucker, S.T. (2002) Environmental change in the Great Plains: an isotopic record from fossil horses. *The Journal of Geology* 110, 123-140.
- 104.** Piller, W.E. and Harzhauser, M. (2005) The myth of the brackish Sarmatian Sea. *Terra Nova* 17, 450-455.
- 105.** Pound, M.J., Haywood, A.M., Salzmann, U. and Riding, J.B. (2012) Global vegetation dynamics and latitudinal temperature gradients during the Mid to Late Miocene (15.97–5.33 Ma). *Earth-Science Reviews* 112, 1-22.

- 106.** Quade, J. and Cerling, T.E. (1995) Expansion of C4 grasses in the late Miocene of northern Pakistan: evidence from stable isotopes in paleosols. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 115, 91-116.
- 107.** Quade, J., Cerling, T.E. and Bowman, J.R. (1989) Systematic variations in the carbon and oxygen isotopic composition of pedogenic carbonate along elevation transects in the southern Great Basin, United States. *Geological Society of America Bulletin* 101, 464-475.
- 108.** Quade, J., Eiler, J., Daeron, M. and Achyuthan, H. (2013) The clumped isotope geothermometer in soil and paleosol carbonate. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 105, 92-107.
- 109.** Quade, J., Garzzone, C. and Eiler, J. (2007) Paleoelevation reconstruction using pedogenic carbonates. In *Paleoaltimetry: Geochemical and Thermodynamic Approaches* in: Kohn, M. (Ed.), *Paleoaltimetry: Geochemical and Thermodynamic Approaches Reviews in Mineralogy and Geochemistry*, Mineralogical Society of America Bulletin, USA, pp. 53-87.
- 110.** Rauert, W., Wolf, M., Weise, S., Andres, G. and Egger, R. (1993) Isotope-hydrogeological case study on the penetration of pollution into the deep Tertiary aquifer in the area of Munich, Germany. *Journal of contaminant hydrology* 14, 15-38.
- 111.** Reichenbacher, B., Krijgsman, W., Lataster, Y., Pipperr, M., Van Baak, C.G., Chang, L., Kälin, D., Jost, J., Doppler, G. and Jung, D. (2013) A new magnetostratigraphic framework for the Lower Miocene (Burdigalian/Ottnangian, Karpatian) in the North Alpine Foreland Basin. *Swiss Journal of Geosciences* 106, 309-334.
- 112.** Retallack, G.J. (2000) Depth to pedogenic carbonate horizon as a paleoprecipitation indicator. *Geology* 28, 572-573.
- 113.** Retallack, G.J. (2005) Pedogenic carbonate proxies for amount and seasonality of precipitation in paleosols. *Geology* 33, 333-336.
- 114.** Retallack, G.J. (2009) Refining a pedogenic-carbonate CO₂ paleobarometer to quantify a middle Miocene greenhouse spike. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 281, 57-65.
- 115.** Robbins, C. (1985) The CaCO₃-CO₂-H₂O system in soils. *Journal of agronomic education* 14, 3-7.

- 116.** Rocholl, A., Schaltegger, U., Gilg, H.A., Wijbrans, J. and Böhme, M. (2018) The age of volcanic tuffs from the Upper Freshwater Molasse (North Alpine Foreland Basin) and their possible use for tephrostratigraphic correlations across Europe for the Middle Miocene. *International Journal of Earth Sciences* 107, 387-407.
- 117.** Rostovtseva, Y.V. and Kuleshov, V. (2016) Carbon and oxygen stable isotopes in the middle-upper miocene and lower pliocene carbonates of the Eastern Paratethys (Kerch-Taman Region): Palaeoenvironments and post-sedimentation changes. *Lithology and Mineral Resources* 51, 333-346.
- 118.** Rozanski, K., Araguas-Araguas, L. and Gonfiantini, R. (1992) Relation between long-term trends of oxygen-18 isotope composition of precipitation and climate. *Science* 258, 981-985.
- 119.** Ryskov, Y.G., Velichko, A., Nikolaev, V., Oleinik, S., Timireva, S., Nechaev, V., Panin, P. and Morozova, T. (2008) Reconstruction of the paleotemperature and precipitation in the Pleistocene according to the isotope composition of humus and carbonates in loess on the Russian Plain. *Eurasian Soil Science* 41, 937-945.
- 120.** Sage, R.F. (2004) The evolution of C4 photosynthesis. *New phytologist* 161, 341-370.
- 121.** Salisbury, F.B. and Ross, C.W. (1992) *Plant physiology*, 4 ed. Belmont, CA. Wadsworth.
- 122.** Salomons, W. and Mook, W. (1976) Isotope geochemistry of carbonate dissolution and reprecipitation in soils. *Soil Sci* 122, 15-24.
- 123.** Schlesinger, W.H. (1985) The formation of caliche in soils of the Mojave Desert, California. *Geochimica et Cosmochimica Acta* 49, 57-66.
- 124.** Schlunegger, F., Jordan, T.E. and Klaper, E.M. (1997) Controls of erosional denudation in the orogen on foreland basin evolution: the Oligocene central Swiss Molasse Basin as an example. *Tectonics* 16, 823-840.
- 125.** Schneider, S. and Prieto, J. (2011) First record of an autochthonous community of fluviatile freshwater molluscs from the Middle/Late Miocene Upper Freshwater Molasse (southern Germany). *Archiv für Molluskenkunde: International Journal of Malacology* 140, 1-18.
- 126.** Sharp, Z. (2007) *Principles of Stable Isotope Geochemistry*, 1 ed. Pearson/Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, N.J, USA.

- 127.** Sodemann, H. and Zubler, E. (2010) Seasonal and inter-annual variability of the moisture sources for Alpine precipitation during 1995–2002. *International Journal of Climatology* 30, 947-961.
- 128.** Stumpp, C., Klaus, J. and Stichler, W. (2014) Analysis of long-term stable isotopic composition in German precipitation. *Journal of Hydrology* 517, 351-361.
- 129.** Tanner, L.H. (2010) Continental carbonates as indicators of paleoclimate. *Developments in sedimentology* 62, 179-214.
- 130.** Tipple, B.J., Meyers, S.R. and Pagani, M. (2010) Carbon isotope ratio of Cenozoic CO₂: A comparative evaluation of available geochemical proxies. *Paleoceanography* 25.
- 131.** Tipple, B.J. and Pagani, M. (2007) The early origins of terrestrial C₄ photosynthesis. *Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences* 35, 435-461.
- 132.** Turco, E., Hilgen, F., Lourens, L., Shackleton, N. and Zachariasse, W. (2001) Punctuated evolution of global climate cooling during the Late Middle to Early Late Miocene: High-resolution planktonic foraminiferal and oxygen isotope records from the Mediterranean. *Paleoceanography and Paleoclimatology* 16, 405-423.
- 133.** Tzanova, A., Herbert, T.D. and Peterson, L. (2015) Cooling Mediterranean Sea surface temperatures during the Late Miocene provide a climate context for evolutionary transitions in Africa and Eurasia. *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 419, 71-80.
- 134.** Unger, H.J., Fiest, W. and Niemeyer, A. (1990) *Die Bentonite der ostbayerischen Molasse und ihre Beziehungen zu den Vulkaniten des Pannonischen Beckens.* Schweizerbart'sche Verlagsbuchhandlung.
- 135.** Uno, K.T., Polissar, P.J. and Jackson, K.E. (2016) Neogene biomarker record of vegetation change in eastern Africa. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 113, 6355-6363.
- 136.** Utescher, T., Böhme, M. and Mosbrugger, V. (2011) The Neogene of Eurasia: Spatial gradients and temporal trends—The second synthesis of NECLIME. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 3, 196-201.

- 137.** Volk, K., Niles, P. and Socki, R. (2011) Covariant C and O Isotope Trends in Some Terrestrial Carbonates and ALH 84001: Possible Linkage Through Similar Formation Processes, 42nd Lunar and Planetary Science Conference, The Woodlands, Texas, p. 1975.
- 138.** Wang, Y., Cerling, T.E. and MacFadden, B.J. (1994) Fossil horses and carbon isotopes: new evidence for Cenozoic dietary, habitat, and ecosystem changes in North America. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 107, 269-279.
- 139.** Wang, Y. and Zheng, S.-H. (1989) Paleosol nodules as Pleistocene paleoclimatic indicators, Luochuan, PR China. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 76, 39-44.
- 140.** Westerhold, T., Bickert, T. and Röhl, U. (2005) Middle to late Miocene oxygen isotope stratigraphy of ODP site 1085 (SE Atlantic): new constraints on Miocene climate variability and sea-level fluctuations. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 217, 205-222.
- 141.** Yang, S., Ding, Z., Wang, X., Tang, Z. and Gu, Z. (2012) Negative $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ - $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ relationship of pedogenic carbonate from northern China indicates a strong response of C3/C4 biomass to the seasonality of Asian monsoon precipitation. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 317, 32-40.
- 142.** Zachos, J., Pagani, M., Sloan, L., Thomas, E. and Billups, K. (2001) Trends, rhythms, and aberrations in global climate 65 Ma to present. *Science* 292, 686-693.
- 143.** Zamanian, K., Pustovoytov, K. and Kuzyakov, Y. (2016) Pedogenic carbonates: Forms and formation processes. *Earth-Science Reviews* 157, 1-17.
- 144.** Zhang, Y.G., Pagani, M., Liu, Z., Bohaty, S.M. and DeConto, R. (2013) A 40-million-year history of atmospheric CO₂. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* 371, 1-20.

LIST OF WEBSITES:

1. <https://skepticalscience.com/print.php?n=2845>
2. <http://clipart-library.com>
3. <http://www.DeepL.com>

LIST OF SOFTWARE:

1. R Core Team (2018). R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. URL <http://www.R-project.org/>.
2. inkscape-0.92.4. URL <https://inkscape.org>
3. MS Office 2010

Appendix-1

Lithological description of the sampling points at Hammerschmiede clay pit

Sampling Point Id	mas	Correlation depth with Irsee (m)	Age (Ma)	Sedimentary description
HAM_A (HR-1)	1.0	109.0	11.663	Soil horizon A; 1.15m dimension; carbonate distribution within 35-80 cm within the base having clay skin; top layer with clay; dark grey to greyish
Marl bed				Soil horizon B; 0.45m dimension; bright grey ; carbonate absent
HAM_B (HR-2)	2.0	108.0	11.659	Soil horizon A; 1.10m dimension; grey to brown molting; carbonate distribution within 0 - 0.5 m; <i>Capea</i> abundant in top
HAM_C * (HR-3)	6.0	104.0	11.643	Soil horizon B; 2.55m dimension; carbonate rare & limited within upper 0.2 m
HAM_D * (HR-4)	6.5	103.5	11.641	Soil horizon A; 1.65m dimension grey to green molting; plant roots upto 4 cm; pyritized; carbonate dispersed; <i>Capea</i> abundant
Coal bed	–	–	–	0.15m dimension; Carbonate absent
–	–	–		Soil horizon A; 0.90m dimension; dark base; <i>Capea</i> abundant; carbonate absent
HAM_E (HR-5)	12.5	97.5	11.620	0.10 – 0.40m dimension; grey to brownish grey; <i>Capea</i> and other shells abundant
HAM_E (HR-6)	15.5	94.5	11.605	4m above top of HAM5 and 3-5 m below HAM4; dimension >2.0m; clay; brown to bluish grey mottled

(*) C & D has no significant dissimilarity; field observation date: 31.07. 2018

Appendix-2

Lithological description of the sampling points from Irsee drill core

Sampling Point Id	mbs	Age (Ma)	Sedimentary description
IR_1	34.30	11.154	Silt marl; [U,fs,t]; bright grey brown; carbonate rich; lime concentration around 30 cm at the top
IR_2	42.80	11.188	Younger upper freshwater molasse; clay to silt; [U,t,fs']; grey to bright grey; slight carbonate bearing; slightly darker at top; little carbonate concentrations at below
IR_3	51.60	11.222	Younger upper freshwater molasse; carbonated clay to silt; [U,t/]; olive brown, grey; very strong carbonate bearing; white carbonate precipitates.
IR_4	54.20	11.232	Clay marl; [U,t/]; olive greenish grey; rust stained; very strong carbonate bearing; carbonate concentrations
IR_5	66.25	11.280	Calcareous clay to silt; [U,t]; olive greenish grey; slightly brown spots; slight carbonate bearing to carbonate bearing; lime precipitation about 66m
IR_6	66.75	11.282	Calcareous clay to silt; [U,t]; olive greenish grey; slightly brown spots; slight carbonate bearing to carbonate bearing; lime precipitation about 66m
IR_7	71.20	11.299	Clay marl; [U,t,fs']; bright greyish olive brown; carbonate bearing to strong carbonate bearing; lime precipitation
IR_8	81.80	11.340	Sand marl; [U,fs,t']; bright grey, slightly olive brown spots; carbonate bearing to strong carbonate bearing; lime precipitation, mica
IR_9	85.40	11.354	Young upper freshwater molasse; clay marl; [U,t/]; bright olive grey; very strong carbonate bearing; lime concentration, partially finely coated
IR_10	89.10	11.598	Lime marl; [U,fs]; olive greenish grey, brown stains; strong carbonate bearing; lime precipitation
IR_11	91.10	11.609	Clay marl; [T,u/]; olive greenish grey, brown spots; strong carbonate bearing; lime precipitation
IR_12	97.80	11.646	Clay marl; [U,t,fs']; olive grey, olive brown spots; very strong carbonate bearing; white calcareous concentration, top 10 cm snail shells
IR_13	100.50	11.661	Clay marl; [U't/]; olive greenish grey to dark olive grey; carbonate bearing; shelly texture, calcareous precipitation, eg. slight humus
IR_14	103.15	11.676	Young upper freshwater molasse; carbonate clay to silt; [T,u/]; olive greenish grey; slight carbonate bearing to carbonate bearing; calcareous precipitation increasing downwards
IR_15	104.80	11.685	Clay marl; [U,t/]; bright olive grey, olive brown spots; strong carbonate bearing; lime concentration, slight hard
IR_16	108.40	12.013	Yong upper freshwater molasse; silt marl; [U,t]; dark olive brown; carbonate bearing; slight humus

Sampling Point Id	mbs	Age (Ma)	Sedimentary description
IR_17	109.10	12.017	Young upper freshwater molasse; clay marl; [U,t/]; olive brown; very strong carbonate bearing; friable structures below lime concentration
IR_18	113.10	12.037	Silt marl; [U,t]; bright olive grey, whitish spots; very strong carbonate bearing; calcareous precipitation, slight hard
IR_19	124.50	12.096	Clay to silt (silica clastic); [U,t]; bright olive grey; slight carbonate bearing; slight hard + layered
IR_20	126.50	12.106	Young upper freshwater molasse; clay marl; [T,u/]; olive grey; very strong carbonate bearing; basal whitish calcareous concentration, above slight hard
IR_21	131.85	12.134	Young upper freshwater molasse; silt marl stone; [Mst]; bright olive grey, olive brown spots; very strong carbonate bearing; fine layered, calcareous concentration
IR_22	138.70	12.169	Young upper fresh water molasse; carbonate silt; [U,t,fs"]; olive grey; slight olive brown spots; slight carbonate bearing; friable textures
IR_23	141.80	12.185	Young upper fresh water molasse; silt marl; [U,t/]; olive brown-olive grey; very strong carbonate bearing; friable textures; downwards calcareous precipitations; slight hard
IR_24	146.20	12.207	Silt marl; [U,t,fs"]; bright grey; very strong carbonate bearing; friable texture

[U= silt; t= clay; fs= fine sand; ms= medium sand; Caps letter= dominant; afore/after= major/minor]
 (Irsee drill core general master data, 2012)
 [WSW Irsee, DFG-FB Irsee, 8029BG015212, Bayerisches Landesamt für Umwelt, 22.08.2012]

Appendix-3

Isotopic data of the sampling points from Irsee drill core

Identity	mbs	Age (Ma)	Age Cluster	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰)	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰)
IR-1	34.30	11.154	ELM	-7.29	-6.24
IR-2	42.80	11.188	ELM	-7.59	-6.01
IR-3	51.60	11.222	ELM	-4.01	-7.21
IR-4	54.20	11.232	ELM	-9.04	-5.48
IR-5	66.25	11.28	ELM	-10.50	-6.06
IR-6	66.75	11.282	ELM	-9.93	-5.85
IR-7	71.20	11.299	ELM	-8.24	-5.34
IR-8	81.80	11.34	ELM	-7.47	-6.08
IR-9	85.40	11.354	ELM	-9.52	-5.61
IR-10	89.10	11.598	ELM	-9.86	-5.77
IR-11	91.10	11.609	ELM	-9.58	-5.98
IR-12	97.80	11.646	LMM	-8.47	-5.45
IR-13	100.50	11.661	LMM	-8.17	-4.74
IR-14	103.15	11.676	LMM	-7.78	-5.51
IR-15	104.80	11.685	LMM	-10.47	-5.57
IR-16	108.40	12.013	MMM	-9.88	-6.09
IR-17	109.10	12.017	MMM	-10.18	-5.78
IR-18	113.10	12.037	MMM	-9.03	-6.13
IR-19	124.50	12.096	MMM	-10.69	-6.01
IR-20	126.50	12.106	MMM	-10.90	-6.62
IR-21	131.85	12.134	MMM	-9.31	-6.38
IR-22	138.70	12.169	MMM	-8.66	-6.94
IR-23	141.80	12.185	MMM	-9.43	-6.99
IR-24	146.20	12.207	MMM	-9.60	-5.81

Isotopic data of the sampling points at Hammerschmiede clay pit

Identity	mas	Age (Ma)	Age Cluster	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰)	$\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (‰)
HR-6	15.50	11.605	LMM	-9.62	-5.99
HR-5	12.50	11.620	LMM	-8.00	-5.89
HR-4	6.50	11.641	LMM	-9.46	-5.83
HR-3	6.00	11.643	LMM	-9.42	-5.77
HR-2	2.00	11.659	LMM	-10.22	-5.74
HR-1	1.00	11.663	LMM	-9.73	-5.71

[mbs= meter below surface; mas=meter above surface]

Appendix-4

C4 biomass (%) of the sampling points

Age (Ma)	$\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (‰)	C4%		
		(Y. Wang & S. Zheng, 1989) ^a	(B. H. Passey et al, 2009) ^b	(K. T. Uno et al, 2016) ^c
11.154	-7.29	33	6	9
11.188	-7.59	31	3	7
11.222	-4.01	56	33	32
11.232	-9.04	20	-9	-4
11.28	-10.50	10	-21	-14
11.282	-9.93	14	-17	-10
11.299	-8.24	26	-2	2
11.34	-7.47	32	4	7
11.354	-9.52	17	-13	-7
11.598	-9.86	15	-16	-15
11.605	-9.62	16	-14	-14
11.609	-9.58	17	-14	-13
11.620	-8.00	28	0	-2
11.641	-9.46	17	-13	-13
11.643	-9.42	18	-12	-12
11.646	-8.47	24	-4	-6
11.659	-10.22	12	-19	-18
11.661	-8.17	27	-2	-3
11.663	-9.73	16	-15	-14
11.676	-7.78	29	1	-1
11.685	-10.47	10	-21	-20
12.013	-9.88	14	-17	-16
12.017	-10.18	12	-19	-18
12.037	-9.03	20	-10	-10
12.096	-10.69	9	-24	-21
12.106	-10.90	7	-25	-23
12.134	-9.31	19	-12	-11
12.169	-8.66	23	-7	-7
12.185	-9.43	18	-13	-12
12.207	-9.60	16	-15	-14

Explanation^a : $C3\% = (2.1 - \delta^{13}C_{\text{Pedogenic CaCO}_3})/14.0 \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (1)$

$C4\% = (11.9 + \delta^{13}C_{\text{Pedogenic CaCO}_3})/14.0 \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (2)$

Explanation^b : $C4\% = \text{slope} \times \delta^{13}C_{\text{CaCO}_3} + \text{intercept} \dots\dots\dots (3)$

Slope and Intercept values for Eq.3

B.H. Passey et al 2009, Supplementary data1		
Age (Ma)	slope	intercept
11.0-11.49	8.43961	67.11
11.5-11.99	8.43960	67.10
12.0-12.49	8.43901	66.51

Explanation^c : $C4\% = (\delta^{13}C_{\text{CaCO}_3} - \delta^{13}C_{\text{C}_3}) / (\delta^{13}C_{\text{C}_4} - \delta^{13}C_{\text{C}_3}) \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (4)$

Where, C3 and C4 refer to the $\delta^{13}C$ values in the respective C3 and C4 endmember. Endmembers should be locally defined with the $\delta^{13}C[\text{CO}_2]_{\text{atm}}$ of concerned timescale. But in this study local endmembers were not available and so global range was considered.

C3, C4 endmember values for Eq.4

After B. J. Tipple et al, 2010 and I. Cojan et al, 2013			
Age (Ma)	$\delta^{13}C[\text{CO}_2]_{\text{atm}} (\text{‰})$	$\delta^{13}C_{\text{C}_3} (\text{‰})$	$\delta^{13}C_{\text{C}_4} (\text{‰})$
11.154 – 11.354	-6.0	-8.5	+5.5
11.598 – 11.685	-5.2	-7.7	+6.3
12.013 – 12.207	-5.2	-7.7	+6.3